

國立臺北藝術大學
文化資源學院
文創產業國際藝術碩士學位學程

International Master of the Arts Program in Cultural and Creative Industries

School of Culture Resources

Taipei National University of the Arts

Master's Thesis

初探觀者身體與物質意涵：
從技術影像的藝術裝置作品進行方法分析

Reading Corporeal and Material Significance:

**A Methodology of Formal Analysis for Art Installations Based on Technical
Moving Images**

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中華民國112年9月

September 2023

國立臺北藝術大學文化資源學院
College of Cultural Resources, Taipei National University of the Arts
文創產業國際藝術碩士學位學程
International Master of the Arts Program in Cultural and Creative Industries
碩士學位考試委員會審定書
Verification Letter from the Examination Committee
第 111 學年度 第 2 學期
(Year 2023 Semester Spring)

We hereby recommend the Thesis Report submitted by Santiago Torres Perez
_____ is qualified for Master's Degree and authorized by the examination
committee.

題目(Title) :

Reading Corporeal and Material Significance: A Methodology of Formal Analysis
for Art Installations Based on Technical Moving Images
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2023 年 6 月 28 日

‘The hardest thing of all to see is what is really there’

-J.A. Baker

To

Lili and Pablo,

Celina and Martin,

Teresa, Ernesto, Alejandra, Diego,
my teachers and classmates at TNUA,
and Jorge Ayala Blanco.

Abstract

This research proposes and applies a methodology of formal analysis for art installations containing moving images. By using this methodology it is possible to identify the elements used in the installation, define their general characteristics within the piece, analyze their relationship including, artistic and non-artistic objects, and analyze the intended corporal and material effects. Following this method provides a set of qualitative tools to determine the degree of relevance of a large set of variables used in art installations, with an emphasis on their role in the construction of time and space as experienced by the visitor, and the materiality of the exhibition itself.

The methodology is applied to two related exhibitions by Taiwanese Artist Zhang Xu-Zhan, the art installation ‘Jungle, Jungle’, and a screening of the short film ‘Compound Eye of Tropical’.

The research finds that the methodology is a useful pedagogical tool for art students, curators, and artists as an introductory level of analysis for complex art installations.

Taipei National University of the Arts

Keywords

Formal Analysis, Art Installation, Materiality, Pedagogy, Zhang Xu-Zhan

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Reading Corporeal and Material Significance:
A Methodology of Formal Analysis for Art Installations Based on Technical Moving
Images

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of study

The goal of this paper is to establish and apply a methodology of formal analysis for Art Installations containing moving images that have used technical devices to acquire their final form.

Art Installations offer levels of complexity varying greatly in form, content, and intent. Art installations based on moving images vary from a simple arrangement of art objects that can be experienced by a viewer standing next to it, to a complex set of circuits of artistic objects, accessible by diverse paths, capable of interaction and audience participation, the *first hypothesis* of this thesis is that a methodology of formal analysis can define most of the variables within Art Installations, describe them and determine the relevance of those variables in the overall piece.

The *second hypothesis* is that through the proposed analysis it is possible to apply a qualitative analysis in the construction of time and space in such installations by considering the relationship between 1) the elements of the installation, 2) the corporeal presence of the visitor, and 3) the materiality of the exhibition itself. The ultimate goal of such an analysis would be to understand the cultural significance embedded in the codes of construction of time and space of Art Installations.

Analyzing the moving images themselves is not a goal of this study, as the formal analysis of moving images has been covered extensively elsewhere. While some characteristics of the moving images will be taken into account, it is the relationships between them and other elements of the installation, the visitor, and the exhibition itself that are central to this thesis.

Art Installations use moving images that come from many artistic practices such as animation, film, light art, screen art, projection art, video games, and virtual reality. The most challenging aspect of this thesis was to find the common ground between those disciplines, as they come from dissimilar conceptual frameworks in their study and practice. Using diverse artistic practices is common in Contemporary Art Installations, in order to analyze complex Art Installations the research couldn't be focused only on one of the fields, for example, Art Installations that use narrative films. The categories included within the methodology show transdisciplinary research from different fields. Most of the

research falls into media studies, while some analytical tools come from other areas of expertise, such as urbanism in the case of space syntax.

Opening the analysis to several artistic practices limited the grade of specificity that could have been achieved if applied to a particular one. This in turn presented an opportunity to use the proposed methodology of formal analysis as an introductory pedagogical tool for students and researchers interested in Art Installations that contain Moving Images, as well as a starting point for artists and curators to describe an Art Installation and its components.

The transdisciplinary nature of this study presupposes readers from diverse fields of knowledge. Depending on the areas of expertise of the reader some subjects will be familiar while others are encountered either for the first time or within a new context, Taking this factor into consideration the research will include the least amount of neologisms and obscure terminology as possible.

That said, there is one major neologism “Technical Moving Image”, This term is necessary as it is broad in the areas it encompasses, very specific in its intent, and there is no other word term that can be applied. While Technical Moving Image might be a neologism used here for the first time, it is directly derived from the term Technical Image coined by Vilém Flusser in his book ‘Towards a Philosophy of Photography’ (Flusser, 2000), and explored in detail in his posterior works, most notably on ‘Into the universe of technical images’ (Flusser, 2011). In the opening line of ‘Towards a Philosophy of Photography’, he defines images as significant surfaces, that is, a surface hosting an abstraction that holds meaning. His understanding of technical images expands in the same line of thought talking about them as images created by machines, while machines for Flusser are in themselves working abstractions, they are tools that simulate scientific theories. Technical Images are then an abstraction of the third order; this kind of image is an abstraction resulting from a process that came out of a mechanical or electronic set of parameters, that are in themselves an abstraction derived from scientific texts. I would like to point out that this is a paradigmatic shift in the appreciation of photography, Flusser does not consider the lens, the camera, and the film tools that capture and store perceptible forces of the world, he sees them as physical interpretations of a human abstraction, capable of producing an image, instead of the common view regarding a photograph as a representation of reality, a proxy, an index. When we see lens-based moving images, especially photorealistic ones it is common to see them as the world, not as a representation. Flusser goes out of his way to point out that Technical Images aren’t even

direct representations, they are first representing a scientific interpretation and then presenting that interpretation. When talking about Technical Moving Images, there is an added dimension; the potential to transform an image over time.

To summarize when talking about a Technical Moving Image (TMI), this research is referring to a surface temporarily inscribed with a meaningful abstraction processed by a technological source, that holds the potential to transform over time. This is the common ground between all the different art practices mentioned above.

An additional *third hypothesis* is that with adjustments the resulting methodology from this thesis can be applied to other modes of artistic practice that use Technical Moving Images, furthermore, by analyzing those adjustments we can understand how a particular practice regards audience corporeality and the materiality of its exhibition.

1.2. Background and scope of research

Two previous versions of the methodology presented in this thesis have been developed as a working tool for my teaching and filmmaking practices, each one broadening its scope. The first resulted in a short pedagogical aid, an online form aimed to help documentary film students to describe their short film projects, by enunciating the intended filmic style, choosing the formal characteristics, and summarizing their narratives. Their films were researched, shot, edited, and exhibited during one semester, it was quite helpful to have students fill out that form before they came into the first advisory meeting, as they had to define by themselves elements that we usually had to work on together for two or three sessions.

The second version of the methodology came as a necessity when I expanded my line of work into transdisciplinary projects and needed a new conceptual framework in order to make proposals for multi-channel screen productions -large-venue rock concerts, virtual production, and immersive displays-. The resulting document was a large and complex form that could be used as the base for a keynote presentation. It became a great working tool to communicate with artists outside of my field.

It is necessary to point out that both previous versions offered production-based intentionality; they contain a series of categories to construct and implement stylistic choices based on a careful balance of conditions, requirements, and resources. Analyzing a finished product as a researcher most of the time leaves us with material evidence that does not overtly acknowledge the scope of the resources used by the artists, how they chose to work alone or had collaborators, their schedule, budget, or even health. Designing a tool

for scholarly analysis has a different set of parameters as it is handling realized options instead of prospective ones. Even if with the intent of production the origin of both previous versions dealt with finished works, and then worked into new categories used for balance and implementation.

Left out from the first to the second version apart from the production-based framework mentioned earlier are a) purely technical data (such as frame rates, codecs, specific models of cameras used), b) all aspects that deal with dramatic storytelling such as plot, characters, and causality.

The research project submitted as part of the application process to the International Master of the Arts Program in Cultural and Creative Industries (IMCCI), of the Taipei National University of the Arts (TNUA) was a “Protocol for Filmic-Style Proposals” that could be valid in various audiovisual fields, its goal was to establish unified criteria that artists could follow to conceptualize and express their intentions systematically and turn it into an audiovisual project proposal. There was at least one step missing, first, there was a need to develop and test that system in finished artworks.

Studying at IMCCI was in part a decision taken with the intention of broadening the scope of artistic knowledge, beyond my previous fields of expertise: film studies and film production. During the three semesters at TNUA, those areas have been complemented with an understanding of curation, media, and performance studies. Being surrounded by a group of international classmates, most of them from the Global South has also played a role in reconsidering vernacular knowledge, global conventions, national identity, and applied directly to my research vernacular forms of display.

The Master’s thesis played a large role in determining the topics chosen for the final papers of IMCCI courses, they became the backbone of this research, as revised sections of those papers are incorporated here. Art Form was the main concern of three papers: “Film Form as epistemic soft power”, “The gray zone goes to the Movies: Film Exhibition in the gallery space”, and “Curating as Decolonization: vernacular modes of Display”. Many of those papers include a critique that will mostly be left out of the thesis but its ontology will be discussed in Chapter 2, even when the methodology can be used outside of it. Other topics informing the thesis explored in other papers are a phenomenological approach to art practice, in the conference paper for the 2022 Symposium of Cultural Resources “Teaching filmmaking as a way of being-in-the-world”, and finally the intersection between national identity, public/private funding, public policy,

and cultural governance written in “Mapping public policy: National Identity and Performance”, for which some revised sections of both are also used here.

1.3. Structure of research

In Chapter 2 a framework for the Technical Moving Image will begin with its philosophical principles, touching upon the Heideggerian notion of Technology as a way of understanding the world and not as an instrument (Heidegger, 2013), how Villem Flusser regards Technical Images as an epistemological revolution comparable only to the invention of drawing and writing (Flusser, 2000, 2011), and a brief introduction of Enrique Dussel’s reframing of phenomenology into the Latin American Philosophy and Aesthetics of Liberation aiming at a decolonized trans-modern future (Dussel, 2022). A fundamental question lies in between form, technology, and colonization of thought, that of concealment of the form, covering the transformation of our ways of understanding.

Next is the analysis of the norms of discourse, production, distribution, exhibition, and reception of technical moving image practice in traditional cinema and (Bordwell, 2006; Bordwell et al., 2003) the avant-garde (Grice, 1977; Le Grice, 1972, 2002, 2011; Manovich, 2002).

Chapter 3 contains the proposed methodology of formal analysis, It identifies the elements used in the installation and defines their general characteristics within the piece, identifies the TMIs and analyzes relationships between them, and then it analyzes the relationships between all elements of the installation including, artistic and non-artistic objects, and finally, it analyzes the intended corporal and material effects on the visitor.

The set of categories of formal analysis is listed in Chapter 3 and has been summarized in Table 1 as a checklist available at the end of this chapter. Summarizing the proposed methodology consists of identifying the elements used in the installation and defining their general characteristics within the piece, analyzing all Technical Moving Images and the relationships between them, analyzing the relationship between all elements of the installation including, artistic and non-artistic objects, and finally, analyzing the functions of the visitor within the time and space of the installation, including the intended corporal and material effects on the visitor. While not all characteristics are relevant to any given artwork, assessing their relevance and intent might be the most relevant qualitative tool.

Chapter 4 consists of a case study of *Jungle Jungle* by Zhang Xu-Zhan, a solo exhibition at Taipei Fine Arts Museum shown in 2022 consisting of several artworks, including stop-motion animation made with paper figures.

Finally, Chapter 5 lists the research findings, possibilities of future research, and conclusions of the thesis.

Formal Analysis Checklist								
Art Installations based on Technical Moving Images (TMI)								
SANTIAGO TORRES PÉREZ								
						Relevant		
Overall Characteristics	Contents	Artistic Objects	Technical Moving Image (TMI)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
			Non-TMI			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
		Non-Artistic Objects	Contextual			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
			Operational			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
			Structural			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Style	Unified Style				<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
		Non-Unified Style	Episodic			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Site Specificity	Site Specific	<input type="checkbox"/>	Site Sympathetic	<input type="checkbox"/>	Site Generic	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Time Specificity	Permanent Exhibition	<input type="checkbox"/>		Temporal Exhibition	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
		Event time	<input type="checkbox"/>		Non-Event time	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Intended Purpose	Private	<input type="checkbox"/>		Public	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Commercial	<input type="checkbox"/>		Non-Commercial	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Characteristics of the Technical Moving Image	Modes of practice	One category of TMI	<input type="checkbox"/>	Several categories of TMI	<input type="checkbox"/>	Mixed categories of TMI	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Movement	Continuous	<input type="checkbox"/>	Episodic	<input type="checkbox"/>	Imperceptible	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Channels	Single-Channel	<input type="checkbox"/>		Multi-Channel	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
		Multiple Single-Channel	<input type="checkbox"/>		Mult. Multi-Channel	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Replayability	Contents play once	<input type="checkbox"/>	Contents repeat	<input type="checkbox"/>	Contents repeat with variations	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Figurativeness	Figurative	<input type="checkbox"/>	Abstract	<input type="checkbox"/>	Mixed	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Image Process Origin	Optical Acquisition	<input type="checkbox"/>	CGI	<input type="checkbox"/>	Other	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Spatial Montage (Relation Between TMI)	Circuits	One circuit of TMI	<input type="checkbox"/>		Several circuit of TMI	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Cotent lenght and scope	Content of all channels intended to be seen during one visit/event	<input type="checkbox"/>		Content of all channels intended to be seen during several visits/events	<input type="checkbox"/>	Content of all channels not intended to be seen even after several visits/events	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Self Contained		Self Contained	<input type="checkbox"/>	Reliant on other objects	<input type="checkbox"/>	Other Reliances	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Syntagmes	Temporal relationships	Total Continuity	<input type="checkbox"/>	Small Elipsis	<input type="checkbox"/>	Undefined Elipsis	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Small Flashback	<input type="checkbox"/>		Undefined Flashback	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
		Undefinable time	<input type="checkbox"/>	Compound time		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Temporal relationships	Total Continuity	<input type="checkbox"/>	Clearly close discontinuity	<input type="checkbox"/>	Total Discontinuity	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Undefinable space	<input type="checkbox"/>			Compound space	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Space Syntax (Relations between all objects)	Following a Path		Single route	<input type="checkbox"/>		Multiple Paths	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Relations between groups of objects		One group of objects	<input type="checkbox"/>		Multiple groups of objects	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Intent in complexity of arrangement		Simple arrange of objects	<input type="checkbox"/>		Complex arrange of objects	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Corporeality	Bodily Involvement of audience		Player Mode	<input type="checkbox"/>		Viewer Mode	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Presence of artists/performers/staff		Present	<input type="checkbox"/>		Not present	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Intended Corporeal Effects	Climate			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
		Odor			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
		Duration			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
		Size			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
		Position			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Other:		<input type="checkbox"/>			<input type="checkbox"/>		
Relationship between objects and visitors		Virtual Agency	<input type="checkbox"/>	Real Agency	<input type="checkbox"/>	Participatory Art	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Materiality	Intended Material Evidence	TMI	<input type="checkbox"/>	Non-TMI Artistic Object	<input type="checkbox"/>	Non-Artistic Objects	<input type="checkbox"/>	
		Spectator			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
		Event			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Industry			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	Intended Material Concealment	TMI	<input type="checkbox"/>	Non-TMI Artistic Object	<input type="checkbox"/>	Non-Artistic Objects	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Relevance of materials used	TMI	<input type="checkbox"/>	Non-TMI Artistic Object	<input type="checkbox"/>	Non-Artistic Objects	<input type="checkbox"/>		

Table 1. Formal Analysis Checklist

2. Literature Review

2.1. Philosophical background

In his highly influential essay “The Question Concerning Technology” (Heidegger, 2013) Martin Heidegger challenges the optics of understanding technology as developing tools, and instead characterizes it as a way of thinking. Advances in technology change our perception, bringing forward or “revealing” characteristics that we couldn’t be able to get before. He mentions the example of industrialized mining, before the developments necessary for it, people would look at a mountain in a way, and after the advent of said advancements some of the characteristics of the mountain were revealed. Now the mountain is a “standing reserve” of mineral resources prone to be taken.

This unconcealment can’t be controlled once it is revealed. A change in our understanding is not in itself problematic. But Heidegger finds that there is a significant risk when it comes to a point in which we see either ourselves or others as resources, as standing reserves of some kind. This change is easy to point out when it becomes evident or starts to overtly affect us, as when corporations change their policies and treat users as resources, as in the case of potential for data collecting that can be monetized.

As technology becomes part of everyday life the initial reveal might get eclipsed. Most urban societies live surrounded by moving images. Images are a form of technology themselves and are a way of transforming, revealing, and hiding. “Images are significant surfaces”, they signify in order to make time and space comprehensible to us as abstractions. Images have a direct effect on us, and the philosopher Vilem Flusser traced a trajectory on the way we have handled these abstractions as perceptual-cultural development with three major revolutions by the introduction of the man-made pictorial image, the written word, and the technical image.

Flusser considers each of these cultural shifts equal in importance, the introduction of drawing during prehistory enabled us to depict our perceptions of the world over a surface. The elements contained in that depiction didn’t have an order, he gives the example of the sun and a rooster crowing, the sun and the rooster did not have chronological linearity, it is not definable if the sun is there because of the crowing or if the crowing is present because of the sun. Magical relations were encouraged by thinking in those terms.

During the Neolithic something changed, with the invention of written language, there was a vectorization of discourse; linearity and causality became part of how we understood the world. How the written language changed humankind was this second

revolution in how we make abstractions of time and space into a surface. The linearization of history and the constant look for cause and effect are part of that epistemological development. During the nineteenth century, after the Industrial Revolution, we changed again with the inception of technical images. We developed programs and constituted them into mechanical or electronic machines, these machines by their programming in turn caused a new kind of image, the technical image. It is not the result of lines drawn over a surface, it is the result of an infinitesimal array of dots, that shows the result of the program of the machine. In photography and film, they were first silver particles oxidized and developed, now the majority of these technical images are made out of a reticle of pixels.

Today moving images are the main types of technical images. Unlike photography they usually linearize discourse. Optically acquiring light through a lens, and the resulting illusion of movement obscure the process, the mechanical or electronic set of rules that rule the machine. In animation or CGI, the representation seems to be the world. That transparency hides a lot of differentiated facts. It seems to present a direct representation, instead of a complex program. What we see is not an image that the author directly passed by its perception, and then coded an image following a set of cultural norms, as would a painting or a poem. It is a technical image; it represents a series of ideas mechanically, digitally, or optically put together into a series of infinitesimal dots, that seem like a sort of objective representation of what it is in front of the camera. It seems like time and space are presented instead of represented. Furthermore, it appears like there wasn't an author with a point of view, and that each shot has been trimmed, composed, exposed, and color-corrected. It hides the fact that an entire industry is behind the mere possibility of a spectator watching the resulting film, and other industries are needed for the apparatus needed for image acquisition.

Human beings forget they created the images in order to orientate themselves in the world. Since they are no longer able to decode them, their lives become a function of their own images (Flusser, 2000. P. 10)

Light by itself is not significant, and the surface itself is not significant either, but applying light to a surface might be enough to make it significant, or applying a surface to light might make it significant.

Technical abstractions put into a surface are not significant by themselves, the user of the apparatus introduces significance into the equation, and the technical abstraction becomes a technical image once significance has been infused.

Technical moving images with cinema at its forefront seemed to linearize non-moving technical images like photography, working almost as a functional equivalent to what writing did after the image in Flusserian terms. That said multi-channel art installations have the potential towards de-linearization of TMIs with the magical return in mind by using each channel as a discrete entity of meaning with significant relations with other channels at the same time.

A strange phenomenon appears as it seems that some codes used for image production conceal the form of the image itself, hiding the very technology that is making it. There are cultural differences towards striving for immersion in an image or moving image environment or underlining its construction, the artificiality of the image, and the apparatus that makes it possible. These cultural differences vary historically and geographically, and they also vary within artistic fields. The study of these traditions, especially those of vernacular forms outside of European and Contemporary American context might help us to understand other cultural approaches beyond immersion.

A framework for a critical cultural understanding of vernacular practices in media has been proposed by Enrique Dussel an Argentinian Philosopher, part of the Modernity / Coloniality Group, a critical thinking collective. Otherness and History are utterly important in Dussel's philosophy; he finds a great division between peripheral and central nations that were either oppressed or oppressors during modernity (Dussel, 2003).

Phenomenologically Dussel distinguishes "cosmos" as the totality of real things and "world" as the real, possible, or imaginary things that exist because of their relationship with humankind. We experience the cosmos by approximation, discovering with our senses, and doing an interpretation referencing the world. In the issue of communication with others, Dussel distinguishes an emitter sending a message to a receiver using a channel, the information contained in the message has a referent, a signification, and is tuned by the receiver as the information received. This does not differ with most semiotic scholars, but Dussel stresses the point of how information has to be encoded using a certain code, during this process, there could have been impediments or resistance. Dussel writes mostly about written or spoken language, he is critical of the whole system of communication and is able to contextualize it in a center/periphery discrepancy. With post-modern systems of communication, vernacular cultural codes from the periphery are not as widely transmitted on a global scale, and mainstream forms of cultural coding from the center get to the periphery constantly.

Center communications seem to drive toward immersion, and by immersing ourselves in them they become concealed. Dussel envisions a new era beyond modernity when peripheral episteme modernity coexists. He sees transmodernity as a way to bring about a more holistic approach to understanding worlds, acknowledging the complexity and interconnectedness between center and periphery and transcending it (Dussel, 2018a, 2022). In the case of TMI, this could point in practice to the use of vernacular episteme embedded in the governance by cultural coding, distribution, exhibition, and consumption.

Dussel points out that the pretension of centrality produces a negation of all other aesthetics that he calls aestheticide, cultural worlds outside of a Eurocentric canon will be judged as brutal, savage, with an undeniable aesthetic ugliness (Dussel, 2018b).

2.2. Double Helix

When studying a mode of practice it is important to understand that it is defined by differentiated contexts (historical, institutional, and discursive) and norms (norms of production, distribution, exhibition, and reception) (Walley, 2008). Austrian artist and curator Peter Weibel wrote about a paradigmatic change within a larger frame within art, in one side he distinguishes ‘Old Art’ as a stage of art centered on objects, in this case, the case of single-channel meant for commercial distribution in movie theaters the film itself, and on the other side ‘New Media’ a stage of art centered on context and observer-oriented experiences, such as Art Installations.

The use of moving images in Art Installations comes from two very differentiated modes of practice, with the two major ones being the Industrial Mode of Representation, a central one in Dusselian terms, and a group of other modes of practice that has been changing in names over time that of ‘parallel’, ‘experimental’, or ‘expanded’ cinema. Over the decades the separation between filmmaking meant for single-channel commercial distribution in movie theaters and other forms of technical moving image exhibition became different artistic practices. This section will explore the differences and similarities of these contexts and norms, from one side the highly standardized Industrial Mode of Representation of the moving image, and on the other the path towards a mode that has been assuming the norms of Contemporary Art.

2.2.1. Industrial Mode of Representation

Even if this thesis is not centered in studying film, it is a common practice to include traditional films in the context of an Art Installation providing a space where it should be viewed as if the visitor was inside of a movie theater. I will state as briefly as

possible this central mode of practice, describing also some of the elements of formal analysis that will be lifted to the methodology proposed by this thesis. One of the major authors defining the IMR is David Bordwell especially in his study of classical Hollywood cinema (Bordwell et al., 2003) and modern Hollywood (Bordwell, 2006). Using Jan Mukařovský's linguistic studies as a departure point David Bordwell characterizes Hollywood cinematographic form in three levels of generality i) Devices, ii) Systems, and iii) Relations of systems. The systems that constitute the IMR are the System of Narrative Logic, the System of cinematic time, and the System of cinematic space. The Industrial Mode of Representation prioritizes the system of narrative logic over cinematic space and time, using them primarily as narrative vehicles.

The emphasis is set on narration, time and space become their vehicles. This in itself is an arbitrary decision that deeply affects the mode of representation and isn't easily seen as this choice and the formal rules associated with it became recognized as 'film language' itself. The emphasis on the construction of a pro-filmic space that encompassed only the screen in which the image is projected rejects the possibilities of cinematographic medium regarding the physical space that surrounds both the image, the spectator, and the projector. Every audience member is meant to disregard this spatial relation that is an intrinsic part of the experience. All spatial relations are reduced to the screen, setting the attention to the frame composition, the montage between shots, and between sequences. The materiality of the entire filmmaking process does not have any weight and is only regarded technically, traces of materiality of the photo-chemical medium such as scratches on the surface of the film, dust, or hair on the gate of the camera or projector were avoided. Most notably the presence of the projector was hidden. The whole construction apparatus should not be apparent. The architecture of the movie theater, the relative size of the screen, the fact of a large audience, and the choice of presenting the film on a flat surface, in a rectangle, on a single screen are supposed to be taken for granted as if there were no other possible choice. The projector is kept hidden, the audience is asked to suspend disbelief, and there is a tacit agreement in the black box to create cinematic illusionism, that involves docility from the audience, author Jean-Louis Baudry describes it as they wish to construct a simulation machine capable of offering the subject perceptions which are really representations mistaken for perceptions (Baudry & Williams, 1974)

Building enormous spatial simulators using lighting, sound and motion mechanisms that were meant to make the audience feel as if they were experiencing a foreign and

distant landscape, as author Andrew Uroskie characterizes it takes someone away from her present time and local space, into the narrative space of the screen (Uroskie, 2014).

Technical developments are fully integrated and made to coincide within the paradigm, usually contributing to immersion as additional narrative devices be it sound, color, or stereoscopic images. Those technical developments are heavily promoted and pushed.

The basic narrative structure is the following: Establish a problem that a character is set to solve, show the struggle as he or she tries to solve it, and finish with a clear resolution that has transformed the character.

The narrative should be centered on an individual protagonist, following psychological causality turning every action into an external expression of inner feelings, all sequences show a clear step towards reaching the objective, advancing the story towards a resolution in a chain of events that present a cause and effect. Every sequence shall be linked to the next one, the first sequence shows the cause, the next one is the effect, which causes the next sequence, and so on.

Narration in Hollywood cinema follows Hegel's view of historical progress, as continuous development and shares this vision with the overall American view of historical progress. This linearization of a cause-effect narrative determines an economy of duration and silence, sequences should never linger too much, and they should state their point and go on so that the overall effect isn't lost (Burch, 1979a, 1979b, 1981)

On another level space and time are secondary to narration even in metaphorical ways. Both the epoch and place of the story function as a backdrop for the individual to reach a goal. Historical events like war or natural disasters are usually set as narrative devices that function as an obstacle in the cause-effect chain.

There are two main driving forces behind the MRI approach that ultimately reflect a set of cultural values driven by its form: a) Every story is oriented toward an individual realizing a goal overcoming obstacles, and b) A stylistic approach that hides all traces of its construction pointing towards total immersion. The paradigm could be summed up as an invisible style that delivers the story of highly motivated individuals who confront a series of obstacles and change themselves in the process.

2.2.2. Non-MRI side of the Helix

Noël Burch stated in detail the characteristics of the IMR mostly as a critical response, or a starting point to study divergent modes throughout film history, stating that

there was a Primitive Mode of Representation (PMR) he followed the development of early local Western European Cinemas (Burch, 1990), as well as the developments of film style in Japan that culminated with the Japanese Mode of Representation (JMR) (Burch, 1979) that reached its peak right before the first World War. Other divergent cinemas studied by Burch encompass the new waves of the 1960s and 1970s (Burch, 1981).

Using Bordwell's own studies we can point to two main factors that diverge from IMR: 1) a different relationship between systems that changes the hierarchy, mostly by getting the system of narrative logic out of the center so that Time and Space can be treated as equal in importance 2) a different mode of causality that is not centered on individuals, psychology, goals, or entirely leaves cause-effect relationship as a whole, examples of Non-MRI film divergent causality cited by Bordwell include supra-individual historical causality in Soviet films, impersonal causality in most avant-garde films, social causality in some German films and films that followed a vital cycle causality in some Japanese films like the ones made by Yasujiro Ozu. Burch on the other hand in his 'Theory of Film Practice' (Burch, 1981) establishes the methodological tools to apply a formal analysis to single-channel films of both sides of the axis -some of them used in the next chapter, in particular, the categories related to style-

The studies of Burch and Bordwell stay in the realm of traditional single-channel filmmaking. Different norms of practice of the technical moving image have been ever-present throughout the decades. The artist Anthony McCall, as quoted by Jonathan Walley, suggested that the worlds of art and avant-garde cinema are like the strands of a double-helix, "spiraling closely around one another without ever quite meeting." (Walley, 2008). This relationship has a long history dating back to the 1920s when parallel to the development of the Soviet Montage and German Expressionist films artists like Man Ray, Fernand Léger, and Marcel Duchamp did their own works of art using film exploring new possibilities of incorporating time-based elements into their works.

The institutional context of art installations that use moving images involves a network of galleries, museums, biennials, festivals, media art centers, curators, and educators. These institutions provide the necessary infrastructure, resources, and expertise to support the creation, exhibition, and preservation of moving image installations. They play a vital role in shaping the reception, curation, and dissemination of these artworks, contributing to their recognition as a significant form of artistic expression. Historically these institutions seemed to make a distinction between avant-garde cinema and films made by artists. Discussing venues and values Gregor Stemmerich (Stemmerich, 2008)

compares how this vision has transformed over time by comparing the distinctions made by Documenta V (1972) and Documenta XI (2002) on their catalogs. In Documenta V films made by artists were published in the catalog while films made by filmmakers were shown but remained unlisted, this seemed to Stemmrich a case of Greengergianism formalistic purity and self-definition of the medium mattered. By Documenta XI there was no distinction in catalogs, While there was a distinction in venues and display, the format and function of the cinema were adapted to the format and function of the white cube and vice-versa, to show the work of Ulrike Ottinger a provisional cinema was built inside a gallery, the presentation was intended to play in a regular cinema, and the work of Steve McQueen was also shown in a provisional cinema constructed inside the gallery space, the film was made with an art audience in mind, and the audience was forced to wait to enter only at the start of the film. Multi-channel works were also shown, they were displayed without the construction of provisional cinemas and the audience could attend at any time, Lorna Simpson's '31' was shown on 31 flat screens, and Chantal Akerman's 'From the Other Side' was exhibited in a gallery space, Akerman had another version of the piece with the same name edited as a feature-length documentary using the same title, Stemmrich states that there was a critique stating that the installation read as an 'advertisement for a great film' using the context as a lobby for cinema.

In the 1960s and 1970s, the rise of video art further propelled the integration of moving images in art installations. Artists began to experiment with video cameras and monitors, exploring the medium's potential for creating immersive and interactive experiences. Nam June Paik took video installation as a sculptural endeavor going experimenting beyond the profilmic space, and often having the visitor as part of the installation, incorporating cameras connected to the monitors. The early years of video art were informed by these real-time bodily experiences, but later artists like Bill Viola repurposed video art outside of that real-time use; by the 1980s and 1990s, it witnessed a significant expansion and diversification of art installations using moving images. Technological advancements, such as the development of digital video and computer-generated imagery, opened up new avenues for artists to explore. Installations began to incorporate multiple screens, projection mapping, interactive interfaces, and immersive environments, blurring the boundaries between film, video, and other artistic mediums. Artists like Tony Oursler, Pipilotti Rist, and Doug Aitken gained prominence during this period for their innovative use of moving images in spatial and site-specific installations.

- Differentiating factors

One of the most prominent avant-garde film movements was that of the 'Structuralist film', highly influenced by formalism and semiotics at first glance structuralist films seem to be stylistic games played with the spectator, by using a handful of elements, lacking narrative and exposing a direct institutional critique by heightening the attention to codes, conventions and the construction of meaning. Duration itself is intended to become evident, and with that other elements such as physical and cognitive awareness of the spectator, and the materiality of the filmic apparatus. A prominent film of this movement is 'Wavelength' (1967) by Canadian artist Michale Snow. A 45-minute single-channel film shot in one room, with the camera fixed on the same position continually zooming, and a soundtrack containing an ever-increasing pitch.

Immersion is not an aim in the art world, the presence of the audience, and the encounter with the entirety of the apparatus, usually reveals what tends to remain hidden in the black box, A common paradigmatic example is Nam June Paik's 'Zen for Film' (1964) showing projector that has a completely transparent film that as hours and days go by eventually projects a collection of dust and scratches naturally produced by the mere act of the exhibition. Scholar Andrew Urosike describes it as follows:

For the spectator first experiencing the film, there is nothing: no image, no sound—nothing to see. There is no “film” there. But after time allows the shock to subside, there is a subtle but totalizing transformation within the spectator's frame of reference. Comparable to the reversal of a figure/ground relationship, Paik's film suddenly appears there where it previously was not. The experience of the bright screen illumination, faintly flickering, suddenly becomes visible as such. One has the experience of simply being present in a particular space, watching light being projected through a moving celluloid strip. (Uroskie, 2014)

When the film was first exhibited the image was almost clear, with time dust and scratches naturally appearing, making the film material an integral part of how it is perceived over time. The space inside the screen can also be called Profilmic space, it can be thought of as a perceptual space, and outside the profilmic is the bodily space. Artists

like Pike bring forward the perceptual and bodily space together, while at the same time revealing the apparatus of its construction, functioning as an institutional critique.

This materiality can also be seen in Rodney Graham’s ‘Rheinmetall/Victoria 8’ (2003), with the projector in front of a screen, showing the image of a typewriter, both the projector and the typewriter have been chosen for their bold design and are aesthetically of equal importance.

Replacing cinematic theory and historical concerns with those imported from the art world situates the resulting films in the realm of Art, with its specific aesthetics, interpretative protocols and critical hermeneutic mythologies. (Betancourt, 2016)

British artist Malcolm Le Grice divided the time/space of a movie into three categories regarding the audience viewpoint (Le Grice, 1972). The events at projection constituted the current “real time/space” of the audience as experienced by the audience. While the events inside the movie screen were a composite of retrospective events, that could show traces of preparatory events, those at shooting, editing, and printing.

Table 2. Malcolm Le Grice’s Real Time/Space during exhibition. (Le Grice, 1972)

On some occasions, artists intend for a projective reading of time, as artist Douglas Gordon did with his piece “24-hour Psycho” a film whose projection lasts 24 hours, and exhibitions showing them usually are required to stay open when film. In an excerpt from an interview published by Kate Mondoloch David Gordon, Stuart’s brother recalls:

Douglas went on to imagine that this ‘someone’ might suddenly remember what they had seen earlier that day, later that night; perhaps at around 10 o’clock, ordering drinks in a crowded bar with friends, or somewhere else in the city,

perhaps very late at night, just as the ‘someone’ is undressing to go to bed, they may turn their head to the pillow and start to think about what they had seen that day. He said he thought it would be interesting for that ‘someone’ to imagine what was happening in the gallery right then, at that moment in time when they have no access to the work. (Mondloch, 2010)

It is possible to say that while watching figurative moving image content spectators experience several real space/times at once, with the possibility of projecting subsequent events to those times during or after the exhibition.

Le Grice (Le Grice, 2011) also studied how Multi-Channel reshapes TMIs, noting that: An often mobile visitor increases their choices of attention, breaks the singularity of experience, breaks assumptions of authorized interpretation based on experience to artistic intention, occupies the same space as that of the presentation and thus the visitor is being aware of occupying space. Le Grice exposes a direct relationship between duration, desire, and intention in the hands of the spectator confronted with a multi-channel experience, he sees an ‘interplay between the spectator’s own motivation -their ‘investment’ of time giving attention to the work- and the temporal experience offered by the work’ (Le Grice, 2011, p. 169)

The catalog for the exhibition ‘The cinema effect: illusion, reality, and the moving image’ goes into multi-channel exhibition several times, a very notable one is the following:

“Julien relies heavily on montage rather than linear plot to introduce complexity and avoid the constraints of narrative cinema. Essential to the delivery of Julien’s montage is its unfolding in three-dimensional space over four screens. Many of the works in the exhibition similarly use multiple screens, in other words, a type of “Spatial Montage”, to enfold viewers in a cinematic environment and perhaps more germane to the topic of alternative models for moving pictures to confront the viewer with a complex range of images and information with which they can choose to engage visually and aurally” (Brougher, 2008, p. 107)

The notion of Spatial Montage was popularized by Lev Manovich (Manovich, 2002), it was originally intended to point out compound spatial relationships within a single moving image, an increasing trend since the advent of digital technology. But, this notion has been expanded as in the book 'Beyond Spatial Montage': which relies heavily on montage rather than linear plot to introduce complexity and avoid the constraints of narrative cinema. Essential to the delivery of Julien's montage is its unfolding in three-dimensional space over four screens. Many of the works in the exhibition similarly use multiple screens, in other words, a type of "Spatial Montage", to enfold viewers in a cinematic environment and perhaps more germane to the topic of alternative models for moving pictures to confront the viewer with a complex range of images and information with which they can choose to engage visually and aurally" (Brougher, 2008, p. 107)

"When multiple independent screens each showing a single image are in close proximity to one another, as with Gary Hill's 1990 installation *Inasmuch as It Is Always Already Taking Place*, the same kinds of relational features of spatial montage emerge but with the additional dimension of actual space mediating the individual nature of each screen, revealing the intimate linkages between a multiplex of screens and multiple images sharing the same screen." (Betancourt, 2016)

Reception of moving image installations encourages active engagement on the part of the viewer. Viewers are invited to explore the exhibition space, move around, and interact with the artwork. This active engagement allows viewers to have a more embodied and immersive experience, as they navigate the physical and conceptual aspects of the installation.

The reception of art installations that use moving images often involves multiple viewings. Due to the non-linear or looped nature of some installations, viewers may choose to revisit the artwork to gain a deeper understanding of its complexities or to appreciate different layers of meaning. Multiple viewings allow for a richer engagement with the moving image installation, as viewers may notice nuances or details that were not immediately apparent during the initial encounter.

Art installations that use moving images encourage individual interpretation and subjective experiences. Viewers bring their own perspectives, emotions, and backgrounds to the reception of the artwork, allowing for a range of meanings and responses. The open-ended nature of some installations invites viewers to form their own connections, narratives, or personal reflections based on their unique interpretations.

Event time can be suppressed in favor of freedom of movement by the visitor. This in part changes how duration is approached and has made overall changes in the norms of practice:

...creating a zone in which the rush of life is slowed, and time is not accelerated but intensified. Fixed camera shots, gradual pans, slowed projection speeds, exacerbated duration, streaming, and looping.

AICTMI often provides opportunities for reflection and contemplation, viewers may take moments to pause, observe, and absorb the visual and auditory elements of the artwork. The meditative qualities of some installations allow viewers to enter a reflective state, engaging with the artwork on a more introspective and contemplative level. By allowing viewers to navigate the space, choose their viewing angles, or interact with interactive elements, these artworks invite active participation. The viewer becomes an active agent in constructing meaning, as their movements, choices, and perspectives shape their understanding and engagement with the artwork. Through the integration of visuals, sounds, and sometimes tactile or olfactory elements, these artworks create a multi-dimensional experience that goes beyond visual perception. The interplay between moving images, ambient soundscapes, or spatialized audio enhances the emotional and immersive qualities of the artwork, deepening the viewer's engagement and contributing to the overall meaning-making process.

When Claire Bishop analyzed how performance changes from the black box to the white cube, she stated how a retemporalization from event time to exhibition time has to occur (Bishop, 2018) in avant-garde performance art. That discipline has also encountered a similar path when practitioners left established venues and found a place in galleries or museums. One of the shared challenges performance artists and moving image-based artists have found when leaving the theater is how to cope with an exhibition that has to be sustained over the whole working hours of a museum instead of sticking to the time of an event.

The same concept can be applied to filmic works as they enter the gallery space. As the images are set on a loop and the visitor may come in at any time of the functioning hours of the museum, it is generally not expected for an audience member to see the entire length of each piece, and if a visitor wanted to see the entirety of a multi-channel video installation time would have to be accounted for each video feed. Other theorists have developed Le Grice's multiple Time/Spaces considerations, dealing with how retrospective and current events are thrown at us, letting virtual and real-time and space be present:

Compared to the cinema's originally disembodied look, the gallery visitor's default value is embodied perception, aware as we are of our surroundings and other bodies in physical space. Also part of 'the body' are the different relations of size, scale, and detail in the museum and on the cinema screen (Elsaesser, 2016)

The reception of moving image installations can also involve social interaction and shared experiences. Viewers may engage in conversations, exchange thoughts, or share their interpretations with others in the exhibition space. The social interaction and the physical construction become as relevant as the narrative construction in the profilmic space.

The norms of reception for art installations that use moving images also include documentation and sharing. Viewers may take photographs, record videos, or write about their experiences to document and share their encounters with the artwork. This documentation serves as a way to remember, reflect, and extend the reception beyond the immediate exhibition context. The norms of reception for art installations that use moving images are characterized by active engagement, multiple viewings, individual interpretation, social interaction, reflection, documentation, and institutional critique. These norms acknowledge the participatory and immersive nature of the artworks and highlight the significance of the viewer's role in shaping the meaning and experience of the moving image installation.

2.3. Critical Curation

In light of the aforementioned considerations it is possible to extend the Institutional Critique further. Contemporary Art modes of practice exhibited inside museums have also been considered a central institution. It is very difficult for peripheral artists to become internationally renowned if they don't speak English, French, or German,

most artists that come from peripheral countries are educated in Europe or the United States. Contemporary Art practices are also determined by curators. The figure of the curator is crucial in the presentation and interpretation of works, selecting, conceptualizing, and proposing a spatial design, between their different functions.

Peripheral curators have questioned contemporary art modes of practice, An example is the exhibition “The Yellow Box: Contemporary Calligraphy and Painting in Taiwan”, curated by Johnson Chang Tsong-zung and including seventy artworks, most of them scrolls, by Yuan Jai, Lee Yi-hong, Hsu Kuo-huang, Hsu Yu-jen, and Yu Peng, exhibited during the months of December 2004 and February 2005, the Taipei Fine Arts Museum.

The concept of the Yellow box was first developed in 2004 at the Visual Culture Research Centre of the China Academy of Art, Hangzhou, by Chang Tsong-Zung, Gao Shiming, and Qiu Zhijie (Chang et al., 2015). The exhibition at TFAM followed a series of curatorial experiments regarding the incorporation of literati traditions in a contemporary setting by Johnson Chang, co-founder of the Asia Art Archive in Hong Kong, where he also founded the Hanart TZ gallery. Since the 1980s Chang has curated Chinese art. In his Yellow Box exhibitions he reincorporates traditional Chinese practices of artwork exhibition, based on the figure of the Literati; members of the educated elite in ancient Chinese society. They were scholars, writers, painters, and officials who were knowledgeable in Chinese culture, literature, and philosophy. As highly respected individuals they often took upon the responsibility for passing down traditional values and beliefs.

Literati painters used brush, seals, and ink to create works of art that conveyed the inner workings of their minds. They believed that painting was an expression of their innermost thoughts and feelings and used it as a way to communicate their views on life and the world around them. The style of the Chinese literati painters did not differentiate painting from calligraphy and poetry, their style was characterized by a limited palette of colors and deliberate brushstrokes. The personal feelings and thoughts expressed by ink were meant as a shared experience, the usual display practice consisted of gatherings where artworks were seen by a select group. Those attending the gathering contributed to the artwork by adding their own poetry, or comments, over the painting itself or by adding a larger comment at the end of the scroll. These paintings were not seen as a finished product when they were displayed, the communal act of appreciating and commenting kept informing the artwork. The artwork was handled during the process of display and

reception, tea was shared among the visitors and the host, music was played, and incense was burnt in the surrounding area. The place of gathering was near nature, or in a garden. The scrolls were often given as gifts to friends, family, and patrons. They also exchanged work with one another. New owners inscribed their seals in the painting. Literati painters also shared their works through painting manuals, which were copies of paintings that could be used as a reference for aspiring artists.

In his long curatorial text for the catalog exhibition published by TFAM (Chang, 2004) Chang explains in detail how traditional Chinese Calligraphy/Painting exhibition differs from the contemporary space of exhibition that he names “White Cube” synthesized here in Table 3:

	White Cube	Vernacular tradition
Display intent	Neutral Purity Unnatural, yet spiritual lighting Site of religious worship	Empathy and closeness between object and person Play-appreciation
Desired effect	Timelessness Otherworldlyness Artwork beyond reach	Lingers and loiters in space and time Artwork at hand
Intended Audience	Audience of enlightened citizens For the public	Audience of like-minded fellows For individual viewers
Subject Matter	Highest values, great moments Situated out of reach	Shifting light of nature Situated in nature
Audience Participation	Look from afar	Inspire viewers to write a poem or comment directly or attached to the work Personal relation
Completeness	Art displayed is whole	Art is incomplete by itself, it becomes whole only with appreciation

Table 3. Tsong-Zung Chang’s difference between White Cube and Vernacular Literati exhibitions.

Chang considers the curator a possible mediator who can maintain a traditional vantage point, interpreting the spirit of literati art in a physical spatial installation, working as a filter for a particular culture of connoisseurship.

He proposes a “Yellow Box” neither spacious as the “White Cube” nor hollow like the “Black Box”, thus creating a space that is neither real nor virtual, a temporal space that

contains the seeds of form, a locus of energy. His proposed box can be a place visited in solitude that is suitable for tea and incense, and if visited in the company of the host/artist the audience will be engaged as guests.

His design proposals follow three general principles a) it has to be as simple as possible avoiding iconography of traditional Chinese Culture, b) Literal imitation and stage-like design should be avoided, c) Direct interference of art like enlargement, reduction, or video display should be avoided.

The materiality of the scrolls is taken into account, and Chang cites its shape as a main factor in the necessity of differentiation from the white cube, as oil painting uses a well-defined canvas, that has a depth that makes it stand out from the wall, and the scroll is ill-defined and frail against a wall.

Some of his design executions contain the following:

1. Free-hanging suspended scrolls, away from the floor, slightly away from the wall. He describes the intended feeling of display as if the scroll was taken out to read as a book.
2. Standard yellow box inside the white cube:
 - If the wall is too tall build a shorter one
 - Couple of chairs placed in front of the artwork with space for tea
 - Back wall behind chairs
3. Implied Scenery
 - Window behind the chair
 - Hints of nature
4. Leaning support to rest while viewing artwork

Other executed designs include scroll tables for individual viewers, viewing frames, hand-scroll drums, low tables to change the body language of the visitor, bending corridors, folding screens, surfaces textured with traditional materials behind the scrolls, on the floor, and as support for artworks.

All the effort put into developing an alternative mode of display inside the White Cube is in itself a losing proposition, as adaptations do not compare to the actual mode of practice. This is clear to Chang:

Modern practices of display and modes of connoisseurship have become critically important for the purposes of legitimation. Modern exhibition practices now represent the dominant channels of legitimation. To be legitimated on its own

terms, to demand to be understood by the White Cube and other western systems, non-modern art forms need to find new channels of mediation, as it means both survival and opening-up to new creative input. The art world has come to accept the White Cube as the universal paradigm, and all aberrations from it to be either ‘resistance’ to, or ‘amendment’ of its restrictions – as in the case of site-specific and community-based projects.(Chang et al., 2015, p. 108)

The Yellow Box exhibitions practice in part the concept of Trans-modernity proposed by Enrique Dussel, to gain epistemic autonomy there is a need to retake the governance of our vernacular cultural forms, building their own systems of legitimation. Peripheral nations have developed a local ontology, epistemology, methodology, and metaphysics, that are in most cases ignored by the center, while on the other hand, the periphery has access to the knowledge of the center.

3. Methodology

Art Installations containing Technical Moving Images (AICTMI) are an art practice that does not adhere to fixed norms of production, distribution, exhibition, or reception, varying greatly in scope and intent. Most installations containing Technical Moving Images have vast amounts of elements, and those elements are related to each other in diverse ways.

Formal Analysis is a great starting point for the analysis of AICTMI since it takes into consideration its elements, the relationships between those elements, and its intended function. Oxford's "A Dictionary of Media and Communication Formal Analysis" describes Formal Analysis as:

"A mode of analysis focusing primarily on the identification and description of the formal features of a text or artwork and on their relations—rather than on its explicit content, or without reference to its specific cultural or historical context.

... this form of analysis can (but does not always) include the exploration of stylistic connotations (including the expressivity of material form, such as brushwork in painting) and the ideological analysis of forms. Formal analysis can only be a partial analysis, since it backgrounds content, context, and audience factors, and as such it may form part of a larger analytical project. (Chandler & Munday, 2011)

As described in Chapter 1 coming from a traditional film production background with some experience in film studies with an emphasis on Formal Analysis aimed for production, I would like to propose a methodology of formal analysis to describe and analyze AICTMI. This methodology aims to serve several goals:

- 1) to discern the elements and characteristics of an AICTMI
- 2) to analyze the relationship between its elements
- 3) to identify the significance intended by the interaction between the piece and the visitors.

The methodology proposed for this formal analysis is subdivided in the following manner:

A) Identify the elements used in the installation and define their general characteristics within the piece.

B) Identify the Technical Moving Images used in the installation, and define their general characteristics within the piece.

C) Analyze the relation between all Technical Moving Images.

D) Analyze the relationship between all elements of the AICTMI, artistic and non-artistic objects.

E) Analyze the functions of the visitor within the time and space of the installation and the intended corporal and material effects of the installation on the visitor.

The rest of this chapter will describe each part of this process, subdividing it into groups of elements that will function as a tool to define each characteristic. While not all elements or characteristics are relevant to a given artwork, assessing its pertinence and intent, is the primordial qualitative tool of analysis. The desired analysis will take into consideration all pertinent characteristics, their relationship with every other significant element, and it will also make it possible to point out how the intended, or unintended irrelevance of certain characteristics shapes the significance of the piece. Every element of the group will function as a guideline to pinpoint how the installation operates, in most of the cases There will be a description of polar opposites of a given characteristic spectrum -such as figurative and abstract imagery, or commercial and non-commercial exhibition- in practice, it is unlikely that the installation will handle a pure archetypal side of a spectrum, as it is most common to encounter something in between. Even if the author, the reader, or the current institutional context might have a particular preference for one side of the spectrum the methodology does not consider any of the characteristics favorable or unfavorable. The list of categories is not mutually exclusive and the order in the list does not signify a ranking in importance of any given characteristic.

3.1. General Characteristics of the Installation

This first part of the methodology identifies and differentiates the elements used in the installation, it then defines the general characteristics of the installation as a whole.

3.1.1. Artistic and Non-Artistic Objects

There is a need to list all of the objects that conform to the piece and those that surround it. This methodology considers two main categories I) Artistic and II) Non-Artistic objects. Several sub-categories are needed for each:

I. Artistic objects

A. Technical Moving Images

A surface temporarily inscribed with a meaningful abstraction processed by a technological source, that holds the potential to transform over time. (See 3.2 for further subcategorization)

B. Non-Technical Moving Images

All other artistic objects such as sculpture, photography, painting, or objet trouvé.

II. Non-Artistic objects

A. Contextual objects

Such as exhibition catalogs, artist statements, wall texts, or audio guides found within the exhibition.

B. Operational objects

Such as projectors, safety signage, and security guard chairs.

C. Structural objects

The architectural characteristics of the exhibition space such as pillars, floors, and windows.

Exhibitions often include accompanying materials to provide contextual information and enhance the understanding of the artwork. They offer insights into the artistic intent, conceptual framework, and technical aspects of the installation, facilitating a deeper engagement and interpretation for viewers.

Non-artistic objects might yield relevance to the overall piece, but they are often taken for granted as they might be easily overlooked. Current norms reception of contemporary art venues has standardized the use of artist statements and curatorial texts preceding an art exhibition. Those texts might have a qualitative impact on how the entire piece is perceived.

3.1.2. Style

For this methodology, style means the consistency of applied artistic choices. By many means and elements, the artist will apply artistic choices that will determine the piece. Within a spectrum of characteristics, we can find tone, color, texture, figurative/abstract content, harmony/dissonance, reticence/exaggeration, symmetry/asymmetry, fragmentation/unity, transparency/opacity, deepness/flatness, sharpness/softness, activity/passivity, randomness/linearity.

Identifying the elements applied, and assessing the consistency of the applied choices yields the style of the piece. The next step is to determine the unicity of style:

I. Unified Style

A defined set of choices that are consistent throughout the piece

II. Non-Unified Style

A style that changes within the piece

A. Progressive development

1. Single progressive development

From a defined starting point to a defined ending point, for example, an installation that starts with figurative content that is sharp and symmetric, and ends in content that is abstract, soft, and asymmetric.

2. Several progressive developments

B. Episodic

Distinct sections in the piece have distinct stylistic choices

C. Astylistic

No stylistic consistency

3.1.3. Site Specificity

Site-Specific Art Installations

Created with a particular location or site in mind, where the artwork responds directly to the characteristics, history, or context of the chosen site. The artwork is designed to seamlessly integrate with the site, utilizing its physical features, architecture, or cultural significance. Site-specific installations usually establish a strong conceptual and visual relationship with the site, creating a dialogue between the artwork and its surroundings.

Site-Sympathetic Art Installations

Site-sympathetic art installations have a harmonious relationship with the site while not being exclusively dependent on it. These installations consider the site's characteristics,

such as its history, atmosphere, or cultural context, while allowing for a certain level of artistic interpretation. In practical terms, the scope, size, and placement of the installation will be shaped by the site, but site-sympathetic installations can be reconfigured or adjusted to different sites without losing their essence.

Site-Generic Art Installations

Designed without a specific site in mind, allowing them to be exhibited in various locations without significant alterations. Site-generic installations are designed to be easily transported and adaptable to different environments. They possess an inherent aesthetic or conceptual value that is not reliant on the context or specific characteristics of any particular site. Site-generic installations can exist as standalone artworks, requiring minimal or no interaction with the site in which they are displayed.

3.1.4. Time Specificity

Permanent Exhibitions

Art installations in permanent exhibitions are intended to remain in place for an extended period, often indefinitely, allowing for continuous engagement with the artwork. These installations are carefully designed and integrated into the permanent exhibition space, considering factors such as architecture, lighting, and visitor flow. Consideration is given to the long-term preservation and maintenance of the installation, ensuring its longevity and continued accessibility to visitors.

Art installations in permanent exhibitions are often part of a larger narrative or thematic context, contributing to the overall curatorial vision and objectives of the museum or gallery. They may be designed to interact or dialogue with other artworks or objects within a permanent collection, creating connections between the installation and a broader set of works.

The exhibitor usually takes responsibility for the preservation, documentation, and presentation of the installation, including educational materials and interpretation for visitors.

Temporal Exhibitions

Art installations in temporal exhibitions are intended to be displayed for a specific period, ranging from days to months, as determined by the exhibition's schedule. Temporal installations can be more flexible in terms of size, format, and display, as they are not bound by the long-term constraints of permanent exhibition space.

Defined Event Time

This type of exhibition is set to a confined starting and ending time, following the norms of exhibition common in several art forms such as film and dance. TMIs presented in this way follow the notion of watching a piece that has a defined beginning and end, and as such visitors are not expected to enter after the start of the event. Parts of the installation such as long-form single-channel films, or complex light art, can be played according to a defined schedule. It can happen periodically, even several times in a day during exhibition days -for example, every hour or every two hours at the top of the hour-, or as special events in the context of a larger exhibition, such as a Biennale.

Art Installations without Defined Event Time

Technical Moving Images in installations without a defined event time are usually playing on a loop and will be shown during the opening hours of the exhibition venue. No special scheduling is needed. The visitor will usually encounter the TMIs at a random point in their duration.

3.1.5. Intended Purpose

Public Exhibition

Most art installations are meant to be experienced in spaces that are open to the public, such as galleries and museums. It could be indoors or outdoors, with or without the possibility of a controlled flow of visitors. Expecting a general audience might have an impact in several areas such as complying with norms of censorship, and accessibility.

Private exhibition

Some art installations are meant for display in private spaces, such as private collections. Usually, this means that the space is not readily available to the public. Not expecting a general audience might free the piece to conform to general norms such as censorship or accessibility, but might also set the piece to comply with private norms and standards.

Non-commercial use

The exhibition of the art installation itself is not meant as a revenue stream for the exhibitor. Even if shown in a space such as a museum where a fee is asked of the visitor, the installation or merchandise associated with it is not regarded as the main source of income for the venue.

Commercial use

The exhibition of the art installation or merchandise associated with it is regarded as a source of revenue for the exhibitor.

3.2. Characteristics of the Technical Moving Image

The second part of the methodology identifies and differentiates the Technical Moving Images used in the installation, and defines their general characteristics.

3.2.1. Modes of practice

Different modes of practice can include animation, film, light art, screen art, projection art, video games, and virtual reality. There are three options regarding the characteristic of a mode of practice in an AICTMI:

- I. Use of a single mode of practice
- II. Use of several modes of practice
- III. Use of mixed modes of practices

3.2.2. Movement

All TMIs hold the potential to generate the perception of movement, either in the profilmic space or in the exhibition space as a whole. Most movies seem to have movement even when they are made from a continuous projection of still images, but even with the same setup, if the same image is repeated it seems to be still. An inverse phenomenon happens with light emitted from a light bulb, electric light cycles on and off at a rate of 50 to 60 times each second, it seems to be constant once it is turned on while it objectively is intermittent, it is only when the intensity or the color changes over time longer periods of time that the light source seems to be moving.

Technical Moving Images have the potential of virtual stillness. We can project the same image over and over again 24 frames a second, creating the impression of a constant source, of a non-moving image. This characteristic of the TMI can give us a range of movement that can be continuous, episodic, imperceptible, rarified, or anything in between.

Olafur Eliasson's "The Weather Project" is an exceptionally good example of a Site-Specific installation that can be cataloged as TMI based, because of its nature as Projection Art, but would be otherwise very difficult to point as a moving image.

Fig. 3. The Weather Project by Olafur Eliasson 2003, Tate Modern. (Peter Marlow, n.d.)

Technical Moving Images' movement can potentially be perceived as

I. Continuous

A type of movement that seems uninterrupted.

II. Episodic

A rhythm alternates between being perceived as continuous or still.

III. Imperceptible

There doesn't seem to be any movement, even if the technical device or the image is moving.

3.2.3. Channels

As stated in the previous chapter the use of multiple channels of TMI has become a staple of art installations, however, it is not mandatory. We can expect the following possibilities:

I. Single-channel

A single-sourced piece of TMI

II. Multi-channel

A discrete arrange of sources of TMI that function as a unity.

III. Multiple single-channels

A collection of single-sourced pieces of TMIs, each of them intended as an independent artwork.

IV. Multiple multi-channels

A collection of multiple sourced pieces of TMIs, each of them intended as an independent artwork.

3.2.4. Replayability

Depending on several factors, such as being defined or not as an event, being generated on the spot, or using randomization effects, the content of the TMIs can be played in the following manner:

- I. Contents play once
- II. Contents repeat
- III. Contents repeat with variations

3.2.5. Figurativeness

Even within the same category of TMI differences in figurativeness can be achieved. From photorealistic figurative representation to sources of colored light.

- I. Figurative
- II. Abstract
- III. Mixed

3.2.6. Image Process Origin

The technique used to generate the moving image can differ if using the same mode of practice, for example, in the case of animation, the process used to make each frame, might come from optical acquisition using a photographic camera and a lens, from computer generated images, using non-photographic image acquisition -for example using an electronic microscope-, or with a mix of several systems.

3.3. Spatial Montage - Relation between TMIs

The third part of the methodology analyzes the relationship between Technical Moving Images. As discussed in the previous chapter the relation between several TMIs will be referred to as Spatial Montage, taking the term from Manovich and Betancourt (Betancourt, 2016; Manovich, 2002).

3.3.1. Relation between modes

Contemporary artists rarely limit themselves to one mode of practice. If there are several modes of practice used in an art installation the relationship between them has to be

defined. Interesting articulations between different modes of practice can be achieved or disregarded, and hierarchies between modes of practice can be set within the piece.

3.3.2. Circuits

Describe how the channels described in points 3.2.3 and their replayability 3.2.4 relate to one another. They can be truly independent functioning as a unit or working as a circuit, be it single or multi-channel. At this point, a hierarchy of pieces can be described.

3.3.3. Intent in content length and scope

As discussed in the previous chapter AICTMIs tend to play with the duration and number of channels to a point in which the piece can not be physically watched in its entirety in one visit, as in the case of '24 hour Psycho' that lasts for a whole day. By analyzing how the TMIs are related between them, the number of circuits, and their replayability, three possibilities can be defined:

- I. Content of all channels intended to be seen during one visit/event
- II. Content of all channels intended to be seen during several visits/events
- III. Content of all channels not intended to be seen even after several visits/events

3.3.4. Self-containment and reliance on other objects

How the TMI relates to other artistic and non-artistic objects is a crucial part of the analysis. TMIs might be self-contained within their single-channel or multi-channel circuit of source, content, and surface, or other objects might be needed, be it to add or to understand.

3.3.5. Syntagmes

This methodology will use and expand Christian Metz's (Metz, 1966) list of categories relating spatial and temporal relationships between shots of film in a sequence to describe the relationship between a circuit of single-channel or multi-channel TMIs.

- I. Temporal Relationships
 - A. Total continuity
 - B. Small Elipsis
 - C. Undefined Elipsis
 - D. Small flashback
 - E. Undefined flashback
 - F. Undefinable Time
 - G. Compound time
- II. Spatial Relationships

- A. Total Continuity
- B. Clearly Close Discontinuity
- C. Total Discontinuity
- D. Undefinable Space
- E. Compound Space

Metz named each combination of temporal and spatial relationships, resulting in two main categories of sequences -Chronological and Non-Chronological-, with many subtypes, of which a few are relevant to take into consideration, the main distinction being that Non-Chronological sequences have qualitative characteristics distinguishing them, as they have to be defined by their content -they are usually montage sequences differentiated by having one or several orders of reality-, while Chronological ones share quantitative characteristics as they are defined purely by their spatial and temporal relationships.

3.4. Space Syntax - Relations between all objects and individuals in the exhibition space

Space syntax is a theoretical framework and a set of analytical techniques used to understand the spatial configuration and organization of built environments. It is an analysis of spatial layout, human behavior, and social interactions within space. It is used mostly by urban planners and architects, but some techniques of space syntax have been studied and applied in the context of museography and curation.

The fundamental idea behind space syntax is that spatial configuration affects human behavior and social dynamics. By studying the connectivity and accessibility of different spaces within a built environment, space syntax can provide insights into how people navigate and interact within that space. It can help identify patterns of movement, areas of congestion, and points of interaction, among other things.

When applied to art installations, space syntax can offer valuable insights into how people experience and engage with the artwork in a given space providing a framework for understanding the relationship between objects, space, movement, and social interactions.

3.4.1. Following a path

The spatial layout, artwork positioning, and interactive elements can guide or disrupt visitor flow, the complexity of an art installation is heightened when it incorporates multiple paths for visitors to navigate, As visitors have more choices and decisions to make the presence of multiple paths can create opportunities for exploration and discovery, but it

can also result in increased uncertainty and potential congestion points where paths intersect or converge. The interaction between the spatial configuration, artwork placement, visitor behavior, group dynamics, external factors, and the complexity of multiple paths amplifies the intricacy of an art installation. As mentioned in the previous chapter there is a direct correlation between the duration or length of a work, the desires of the visitor, and their intentions to explore it. Analyzing the possible flow of the visitor starts with a quantitative distinction:

- I. A single route to be taken
- II. Intended Possibility of Multiple Paths

After that step a qualitative analysis of how that decision has been made has to be made, taking into account previous layers of analysis.

3.4.2. Relations between groups of objects

As in the previous element of the analysis, there is a qualitative component of how artistic and non-artistic objects relate to each other, namely:

- I. One group of objects
- II. Multiple groups of objects

And, after a qualitative analysis is required.

3.4.3. Intent in the complexity of the arrangement

Both of the previous elements can yield a qualitative analysis to determine if the AICTMI adheres to the following criteria and make a distinction of its use:

- I. Simple arrangement of objects
- II. Complex arrangement of objects

3.4.4. Corporeality

As stated throughout this paper corporeality plays a crucial role in art installations as it expands the scope of the artwork beyond visual observation, as it can foster an embodied and participatory experience. It can target several responses such as immersion when the apparatus is hidden or institutional critique when the apparatus is exposed.

- Bodily Involvement of the Audience

From 2016 to 2019 the research project and associated exhibition "Reset the Apparatus! A Survey of the Photographic and the Filmic in Contemporary Art." explored the intersection of photography and film in contemporary art practices. It categorized two modes of bodily involvement of the visitor to an exhibition:

- I. Viewer mode

When visitors assume a passive position, observing and interpreting the artworks as spectators. They primarily rely on visual perception and subjective interpretation to understand and appreciate the exhibited works. Viewer mode emphasizes the contemplative and reflective nature of experiencing art.

II. Player mode

‘When the viewers themselves physically interacted with the viewing device so that the users’ bodies became part of the machine’s functioning’ (Lissel et al., 2019). This could involve physical engagement, manipulating elements, or even assuming performative roles within the exhibition. Player mode emphasizes the immersive and experiential aspects of contemporary art, blurring the boundaries between the viewer and the artwork.

- Presence of the artist or staff

Up to this point the paper has hardly acknowledged the possibility of the presence of the artists in the installation, be it as part of the event, or as a performer along with TMI. It doesn’t have to be the artist itself, as others might be asked to perform for the piece. There is also the case that staff is needed for example when VR headsets and other technically complex TMI exhibitions take place. The presence of these individuals who are not visitors might alter the experience of the piece to the visitor be it intentionally or unintentionally.

- Intended Corporeal Effects

Some installations aim to trigger corporeal responses. Many techniques can be used starting with the control of elements of the TMI like size, duration, or the position of the artwork related to that of the audience. However, the control of other elements such as climate control, the odor of the exhibition space, relative humidity, the use of sound, or direct contact of the materials used in the installation with the visitor, might be used as part of the installation.

- Relationship between objects and visitors

Several types of interactions offer varying degrees of agency, control, and participation within art installations. Each approach creates unique dynamics, influencing the relationship between the audience and the artwork, and shaping the overall experience for participants.

I. Virtual Agency

Virtual agency refers to the illusion or perception of having control or influence within a virtual or simulated environment. It is a form of passive engagement where

individuals delegate their active participation to external entities or mechanisms. Visitors passively observe or experience the artwork without actively engaging while thinking that they are, by relying on pre-programmed or automated interactions provided by the artwork itself or other participants, relinquishing their own agency in the process.

II. Real Agency

Actual, tangible actions and decisions made by visitors that impact the installation. It goes beyond the perception of control and involves physical engagement, manipulation of objects, or direct participation in the creation or transformation of the artwork. Real agency empowers visitors to actively shape the evolving nature of the installation.

III. Participatory Art

Participatory art involves active involvement and collaboration between the artist, the artwork, and the audience. It encourages viewers to become active participants, co-creators, or contributors to the artwork. Participants are invited to engage physically, intellectually, or emotionally, often through interactive elements, performative actions, or dialogue. Participatory art blurs the boundaries between artist and audience, fostering a sense of community, shared authorship, and collective experience.

3.4.5. Materiality

As stated in the previous chapter, materiality can be present inside and outside the profilmic space, concealing the materiality of a piece can function as a tool for immersion while revealing the material nature of a piece, of its exhibition, and its surroundings, can function as a tool to make the construction evident, imposing a 'Brechtian' distance to make the visitor self-aware.

There might also be significance in the materials used, both in the artwork or the exhibition. Why and how a material is selected could inform the overall perception of the piece.

- Intended Material Evidence

For this methodology, a factor to take into consideration is where the material evidence has been intended:

Artistic Object (TMI or Non-TMI), Non-Artistic Object (Contextual, Operational, Structural)

A qualitative assessment of how this intended material evidence unconceals the apparatus and at which level it operates, as it might reveal the presence of the craft, the event, the industry, or the ontology.

Each level can reveal for example the presence of the other, the projector, the architecture, the ideological system, or even the economic system required to bring the exhibition into existence.

- Intended Material Concealment

It is often taken for granted that much of the artist's craft has to do with making the technique required for his artworks invisible. Since the Renaissance until modernity Western art, specifically visual art, and entertainment, has aimed toward immersion of the visitor into the artwork. It operates at different levels and ultimately requires suspension of disbelief from the visitor. First, the visitor is supposed to disregard other individuals, then the apparatus that makes the exhibition possible, and after a point the artistic technique in the artwork.

For this methodology, there is a need to check if material concealment is intended and if this is relevant to the piece.

- Relevance of materials used

Tactile reactions, or other bodily responses might affect the response of the visitor, by the use of the materials in an Artistic Object (TMI or Non-TMI), Non-Artistic Object (Contextual, Operational, Structural including elements of the architecture of the exhibition space). Materials can also be relevant to cultural codes, such as changing the perception of value of an object by using very expensive or inexpensive materials, using materials that are perceived as sacred or taboo such as human remains, or vernacular use of materials that yield significance to the piece.

4. Case studies

The proposed methodology described in the previous chapter will be applied to two related artworks by Taiwanese Artist Zhang Xu-Zhan. The first one is an art installation based on Technical Moving Images titled ‘Jungle, Jungle’ exhibited at Taipei Fine Arts Museum, and the second one is the short stop-motion film ‘Compound Eyes of Tropical’ exhibited in a movie theater at Taiwan Film and Audiovisual Institute. The Installation was selected first, it is large and complex without being unmanageable. It contains several TMIs related to each other. The materials used are relevant to the overall piece. It was exhibited in a prestigious venue that constantly showcases local artists relevant to national, regional, and international audiences.

A second case study from a different mode of practice was also planned for this research, to compare, contrast, and test the methodology outside of art installations. One of the most relevant elements in ‘Jungle, Jungle’ is the 17-minute short film itself ‘Compound Eyes of Tropical’, which has been exhibited in several film festivals and won the best animation short film at Taiwan’s 2022 ‘Golden Horse Award’, one of the most prestigious film awards in the region.

Born in 1988 Zhang Xu-Zhan graduated from Taipei National University of the Arts, studying Animation as an undergraduate and New Media as a graduate. His professional work has been informed by both modes of practice. He is a rare example of an artist capable of growing and maintaining relevance in both fields.

Whenever possible the analysis will use only the elements present in the exhibition, including contextual objects such as the guidebook and audioguide, without consulting other sources. This won’t be possible in its entirety as further cultural context -such as the use of paper in religious practices in Taiwan- is needed.

The moving images in the profilmic space will not be analyzed, as explained in Chapter 1 there are specific formal analysis methodologies that are better suited especially in the case of single-channel narrative films, and the current methodology aims to analyze the relationship between the elements of the AICTMI, the corporeal presence of the visitor, and the materiality of the exhibition.

4.1. 'Jungle, Jungle' by Zhang Xu-Zhan

4.1.1. General Characteristics

'Jungle, Jungle' was temporarily shown in 2022 from 08/20 to 11/13, on the third floor of the Taipei Fine Arts Museum(TFAM), it used rooms 302, 303, and part of 304, collectively known as Gallery 3A. 'Jungle, Jungle' was a non-commercial public exhibition following the Museum's guidelines. TFAM was founded in 1983 as the official art Museum of Taipei, it is dedicated to modern and contemporary art its main missions are 'to promote the preservation, research, development, and popularization of Taiwanese modern and contemporary art' (TFAM, 2023), the museum also aims to introduce the local audience to international art currents. During the same period, other three temporal exhibitions shared the same floor, they were connected by a central corridor, each exhibition displayed its own graphical identity shown in the typography and colors used on the title of the exhibitions and names of the artists, as well as the color of the wall and font itself. Every exhibition also showed a different approach to lighting designs and some, as in the case of 'Jungle, jungle' also had contextual objects before entering the room, as shown below in figures 2 and 3.

Figure 2. Entrance to 'Jungle, Jungle' exhibition. (Contextual objects on the right side)

Figures 3. Entrance to 'Jungle, Jungle' exhibition

Referring to the studied case the entrance showed several elements: a green front wall with an open door arch in the middle, showed three elements distinctly lit with overhead light, on the left side the texts ‘Jungle, Jungle’, ‘ZHANG XU zhan solo Exhibition’ in large white typographies, in both Chinese and English, on a lower size font there were some other credits, on the right side a brief guidebook and a QR code to download a digital version of the guidebook, and in the center entering the door, broken pieces of mirror. The reflection effect of the broken mirror with the overhead light was notorious on the wall.

Figure 4. TFAM third floor Floorplan

All sources of natural light were covered, Room 302 hosted the entrance and was subdivided into two interconnected rooms A and B, Room B itself was interconnected to rooms 303 (C) and 304 (D), as shown above in Figure 4. Standing in any of the rooms did not let the visitor see the content from another room. Most lighting was done overhead with spotlights that could be seen clearly on rails on the ceiling. Several of the artworks had identification labels, ‘Compound Eyes of Tropical’ has a summary of its narrative on the identification label.

A floorplan of the exhibition space was provided in the guidebook and can be seen below in Figure 5, In the floorplan some of the artworks are mentioned and assigned to each room, the nomenclature used in the guidebook will be followed using Arabic numerals to 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 to refer to the artworks numbered on the guidebook, Roman numerals I, II, III, and IV will be used to refer to artworks without an assigned number and are referred to in the revised floor plan shown in Figure 6. The guidebook itself is only four pages long, it provides technical information on the artworks that will be cited after the

Room	Artwork	TMI/Non-TMI	Figure
A (302)	1- Lake Stage-Animal Story Series Medium Mixed media Year 2022 Size - 730 x 244 cm	Non-TMI	9, 10
A (302)	2- Shadow Stage-Animal Story Series Medium Mixed media Year 2022 Size - 200 x 450 cm	Non-TMI	11
A (302)	3- Holy Mountain-Animal Story Series Medium Mixed media Year 2019 Size - 350 x 350 cm	Some TMI elements	12
B (302)	5- Wolf and Tiger and others Medium Single channel video Year 2022	TMI	19
C (303)	4- Compound Eyes of Tropical Medium - Single Channel video, color, sound Year 2020-2022 Duration 16 minutes	TMI	20, 21
D (304)	6- Untitled Medium - Single channel video installation, 4K, color, sound Year 2020 - 2022 Time - Loop 6a- Additional non-TMI elements include shattered glass and insect like puppets	TMI, with some Non-TMI elements (6a)	22, 23
A (302)	I - Costumed Figures-Animal Story Series Medium Mixed media Year 2019 - 2022 Size - Dimensions Variable	Non-TMI	15
A,B,C (302, 303)	II - Musicians-Animal Story Series Medium Mixed med. Year 2019 - 2022 Size - Dimensions Variable	Non-TMI	13, 14
C (304)	III- Paper Skin Medium - Newspapers of various languages, paste, wood board, PP board Year 2022 Size - Dimensions variable	Non-TMI	16, 17, 20, 21
Entrance (302)	IV- Untitled (Unlisted) Shattered glass Year 2022 Size- Dimensions Variable	TMI	4, 5, 18

Table 4. List of Artistic Objects in 'Jungle, Jungle'

The style of the piece as a whole is unified, all artistic objects that are non-TMIs, as well as the content of the TMI inside the profilmic space, share a handcrafted appearance, seemingly rough surfaces made of paper, bits of thin layered plastic, or shattered mirrors, this is evident even in the most abstract pieces such as ‘Paper skin’ which its surfaces show only newspaper, and the untitled shattered glass at the entrance. The more figurative works show slim and angular anthropomorphic puppets of either animals or puppets of people representing anthropomorphic animals, There are also accessories for the puppets such as musical instruments, and there are other elements conforming to the environment where the puppets are placed, such as rivers, mountains, and trees, all of these elements are slightly asymmetric, use subdued tones of color, with a predominating earthly and green color palette. The overall tone is somber. That said, each room has a different ambiance and changes slightly in tone, rooms B, C, and D are conditioned specifically for video projection. The size and scope of the pieces seemed to be tailored for TFAM’s Gallery 3a, even if the exhibition could be mounted in other places some elements seem to be built specifically for the site, especially III ‘Paper Skin’, making the exhibition Site-Sympathetic.

For the purpose of this research, the description of artworks will be divided into two, those based on Technical Moving Images and Non-TMI. Non-TMI will be discussed first, as TMIs have a larger section below. Before going into the artworks contextual information available for the exhibition will be cited. It is necessary to remark that all the contextual data provided is the same that the visitor could access at the exhibition itself. The only data that will not be discussed here is the audio guide since it was available in Mandarin Chinese only, and non-Chinese speakers would miss this content too.

- Context on the artist Zhang Xu Zhan:

‘Born 1988, into the popular century-old Hsin-Hsing Paper Sculpture Store in Xinzhuang, Taipei County, Zhang Xu Zhan specializes in creating a riotous profusion of paper effigies ranging from luxurious mansions and oversized paper dolls to paper-pasted mythological animals and flowers.

His artworks not only revolve around absurd and bizarre images, but also encapsulate his wry observations on strange social phenomena and the cul-de-sac his family business (memories) faces. transforming all kinds of contemporary life

experience into surreal, bizarre images. In other words, the artist's works feature the unending decay and the post-revelry companionlessness that serve as part of his life's rich tapestry.

Earning his master's degree in new media art from Taipei National University of the Arts (2016).' (TFAM, 2022)

- Context on the exhibition itself:

'A rabbit, fox, mouse deer, crocodile and crab they dance and leap with the music — different animal figures appear and interchange in rapid succession. As we come close to discovering a story that is familiar to us within Zhang Xu Zhan's video work, the characters suddenly transform into another appearance. This imaginary space that portrays familiarity and fluidity began from Zhang Xu Zhan's 2017 video work Si So Mi. In this work the artist explored the universal and fluid aspects within Taiwan's cultural landscape, discussing similar stories that have evolved out of a collective consciousness from different corners of the world. Zhang Xu Zhan views the framework of these stories as a container, where individuals can freely fill in the storyline according to their own life experiences and cultural background.

The exhibition Jungle Jungle developed from Zhang Xu Zhan's 2018 artwork Animal Story Series, which was based on the artist's research conducted the same year, during his time as artist in residence in Southeast Asia. In Malay culture, the mouse deer is a common folktale character, well known in the tale of the 'Mouse Deer Crosses the River'. The story narrates a clever mouse deer tricking a river full of crocodiles to line up in a row, allowing the mouse deer to jump across their backs, safely crossing the river to eat the fruits on the other side. Around the world, there are many tales about a small but clever animal outsmarting other animals in a battle of wits; not only is there the mouse deer counting crocodiles to cross the river, the protagonists change to reflect the natural environment and historical

background of each place. For his video work *Compound Eyes of Tropical*, Zhang Xu Zhan created a riverbank scene, combining folktales with shared motifs collected by the artist from different regions. Imagery of different animal forms interchange rapidly, expanding the space for interpretation.

The artworks displayed in *Jungle Jungle* extend from the video work *Compound Eyes of Tropical*. The first exhibition room displays the sculptural installation *Lake Stage*, reassembled from the set design used in the video work. Placed within the installation are a number of figures wearing 'yinhén' costumes, reflecting the uniqueness of Taiwan's traditional folk art, while the installation *Holy Mountain* portrays a band of musicians playing the gamelan and Chinese drums surrounding an enigmatic lake scene. The two video works *Untitled* and *Wolf and Tiger and Others*, extract key plot elements from *Compound Eyes of Tropical*, allowing audiences to wander through multiple areas within the jungle, navigating a fragment-like visual experience to assemble their own unique perspective.' (TFAM, 2022)

There are several elements that are highlighted by getting contextual information, they validate the project's cultural significance, cement the narrative, and narrow ambiguity. Cultural significance is developed at several levels, first, the cultural significance of the artist's background and the materials used, mentions of his previous works and study, then the cultural significance of the content of the exhibition discussing the starting point used by the artist, the Malay folktale 'Mouse Deer Crosses the River' and how the artist mix it with regional and national elements, links between Southeast Asia, indigenous Taiwanese, and Chinese cultures are a notable subtext of contextual information. The contextual information solves the ambiguity of the anthropomorphic animal puppets, their identities are defined as 'rabbit, fox, mouse deer, crocodile and crab', references to musical instruments are clearly defined, so are the actions that are taking place, and the fact that figures are wearing costumes. Finally, the narrative is told in its simplest form: 'The story narrates a clever mouse deer tricking a river full of crocodiles to line up in a row, allowing the mouse deer to jump across their backs, safely crossing the

river to eat the fruits on the other side'. Most of the elements discussed in the contextual information can be applied to 'Compound Eyes of Tropical' itself, as content regarding 5, 6, and IV are not overtly mentioned, this will be further discussed when analyzing the relationship between TMI.

Artworks 1, 2, and 3 are contiguous, without separation between them. They share a large surface that occupies most of room A in what seems to be a seamless stage representing a lake, a mountain, and several peaks, on them are various groups of characters; it seems to be either costumed figures (I) or musicians (II) with diverse actions. Most of the artworks are labeled as "Animal Story Series", it is not easy to see where one action or artwork ends and the other begins. Throughout the large "landscape" in room A there are small caves and valleys that hold individual figures and small groups. There are some notorious differences as seen in figure 7, the setting of artwork 1 'Lake Stage-Animal Story Series' is the aforementioned lake and its shore, the action retells the folktale 'Mouse Deer Crosses the River' with several groups of figures dressed as antagonistic animal characters, one figure performing the crossing of the river as a prey (rabbit, mouse deer) and several as predators (crocodile, crab), the most notable is the line of crocodiles. Figure 8 shows a detailed view of a figure and a crocodile costume. The overall central piece of room A functions as a diorama.

Figure 7. General view of Artwork 1 'Lake Stage-Animal Story Series'

Figure 8. Detail view of Artwork 1 ‘Lake Stage-Animal Story Series’

The end of the lake gives way to the second artwork ‘Shadow Stage-Animal Story Series’. Seen from the front of the room its most recognizable feature is a round plastic screen displaying what appears to be a projected still shadow of the silhouette of the Mouse Deer in the middle of the mountain as seen in Figure 9.

Figure 9. View of Artwork 2 ‘Shadow Stage-Animal Story Series’

Artwork 3 includes moving lights representing torches as seen in Figure 10. The resource of moving light is used only in this part of the diorama.

Figure 10. View of Artwork 3 ‘Holy Mountain-Animal Story Series’

Artworks of series II are used in the diorama some as groups of animal musicians are present, with paper representations of a Gamelan ensemble as shown in Figure 11. There are other groups and individual figures with drums or percussion instruments. Around rooms A, B, and C mounted on the wall or at the top of a base individual characters of series I can be found, such as the one shown in Figure 12. In room A there are also groups of figures from artwork series I in the diorama and individual figures mounted on the wall such as the one shown in Figure 13.

Figure 11. View of Gamelan Ensemble Artwork II ‘Musicians-Animal Story Series’

Figure 12. View of Artwork II ‘Musicians-Animal Story Series’ mounted on wall

Figure 13. View of Artwork I ‘Costumed Figure-Animal Story Series’

Around the walls and ceiling of room C artwork III ‘Paper Skin’ is displayed, it mimics the texture of the diorama in a larger context and completely surrounds artwork 4.

When traversing the small corridor connecting rooms B and C the artwork might give the impression of traversing into a cave, when seen up close it is notorious that the paper used comes exclusively from newspapers written in several languages, with a diversity of alphabets and writing systems. Figure 14 shows a detail of the artwork, while Figure 15 shows the entrance from room B, ‘Paper Skin’ can also be seen in Figures 18 and 19 surrounding ‘Compound Eyes of Tropical’.

Figure 14. Detailed View of Artwork III ‘Paper Skin’

Figure 15. View of Artwork III ‘Paper Skin’ from room B

4.1.2. Characteristics of the Technical Moving Images

There are four artworks based on Technical Moving Images in the exhibition, three of them are based on stop-motion animation (Artworks 4, 5, and 6 in Table 4), and one of them (IV) is based on light art.

Artworks 4, 5, and 6 were all single-channel videos, projected in darkened rooms, each of them conditioned to a different degree. All content in the profilmic space was acquired optically and featured a figurative representation using paper models in stop-motion animation. The movement is perceptible and almost continuous, small imperfections are present as part of a handmade technical process common to stop-motion animation. In all cases, content is repeated without variations.

Artwork 4 had a provisional cinema built for the projection of a several-minute-long animation, four speakers were used at both sides of the screen to output sync sound from the short film, the short film repeated regularly, it displayed a countdown before the next projection, this let the previous audience empty room C and make way for a new group of visitors. Artworks 5 and 6 were shorter looped videos that repeated seamlessly.

Artwork IV was kept unreferenced in the guidebook and all other contextual documents, it does not have an identification label, yet it functions as the first and last artistic object of the exhibition. As shown below in Figure 16 it consists of triangular pieces of shattered mirrors, illuminated from above, showing reflected light. Movement is imperceptible and continuous at 60hz per second. Without any context, the content appears to be abstract.

Figure 16. Detailed View of unreferenced artwork (IV)

As seen in Figure 17 artwork 5 is displayed on a vertical screen at the back of room B, the darkest spot in the room, the projector is not visible. These two speakers output audio in the room, near the entrance to room C. Profilmic content includes several insects on top of each other blown by the wind as a solitary insect approaches and becomes part of the group, as a background a surface similar to the circular screen prominent in artwork 2 and 5 (figure 9 and 19) changes as shadows of predator and prey are projected into it.

Figure 17. View of Artwork 5 ‘Wolf and Tiger and Others’

Artwork 4 is displayed on a horizontal screen on the north side of room C, the projector is not visible. Opposite to the screen are long wooden benches intended for visitors to seat. The profilmic follows the narration described on the contextual objects described previously, adding to that description it is relevant to say that the editing implies that the same anecdote occurs to several preys and predators, pushing the narrative of a ritual that works as a metaphor of a right of passage in which a member of a vulnerable group (prey) faces its opposite (predator). In the end, the figure representing the prey loses a limb and becomes a shattered mirror.

Artwork 4 is surrounded in its walls and ceiling by Artwork III, and on top of the speakers are individual figures of Artwork II, as shown in Figures 18 and 19.

Figure 18. View of Artwork 4 ‘Compound Eyes of Tropical’

Figure 19. View of Artwork 4 ‘Compound Eyes of Tropical’

Artwork 6 is displayed in a very dark room, the only sources of light are the projector casting a prominent beam from the west part of the room to a large double-sided screen, and an overhead light fixture dimly lighting the southeast corner of room D, displaying a Non-TMI element of insects over shattered mirrors, as seen on figure 20. The

profilmic content on the double-sided screen has an animated version of the shattered cristal-like surface and insects around it moving slowly.

Figure 20. Detail of Non-MRI element of Artwork 6 'Untitled'

Figure 21. View of Artwork 6 'Untitled'

4.1.3. Spatial Montage

There is a clear hierarchy between TMI artworks on ‘Jungle, Jungle’. Artwork 4 ‘Compound Eyes of Tropical’ works as a central artwork, carrying most of the narrative, discursive, and stylistic elements, all other TMI artistic objects add on to ‘Compound’. This is evident even in the content length and scope of each piece, artwork is several minutes long, with several sequences, characters, and actions, while artworks 5 and 6 happen all at a single location with a limited set of models. Artworks 5, 6, and IV are reliant on artwork 4, as they gain their full significance only after it has been entirely watched. In the case of artwork IV, it even re-contextualizes the piece from an entirely abstract artistic object to a figurative representation, instead of mere reflections on a wall it becomes the final embodiment of the protagonist as it failed its rite of passage.

There is a temporal continuity between most TMI artistic objects, artworks 6, and IV happened after the end of ‘Compound Eyes of Tropical’. There is an undefined ellipsis between 4 and the other two artworks. Temporarily artwork 5 is difficult to place, it can work as a premonition of what will happen in ‘Compound’. Spatially there is a close discontinuity between 4, 5, and 6, while IV jumps from the profilmic to the outside of the profilmic space.

The same hierarchy shown between artworks can be applied to the TMI modes of practice as it is possible to call stop-motion animation the main mode, while screen art and light art are used to complement and echo the intentions of stop-motion. The content of all channels is intended to be seen during one visit, and it seems that choosing a non-chronological order is encouraged so that the resignification of several artworks can occur and that means that re-watching the shorter TMI artworks works in favor of the exhibition and it is part of the artist intentions.

Each single-channel experience differs in its self-reliance and constitutes a circuit as a whole. Artwork 4 is surrounded by other artworks, including the large ‘Paper Skin’ and the small ‘Musicians’ on top of the speakers, it does rely on other non-TMI objects, while Artwork 6 reveals the projector and the screen, relying on other TMI objects, revealing and embracing the apparatus, thus partially refuting the suspension of disbelief that 4 required, repeating a variant of the same element on the profilmic and outside the profilmic space can also signal the representation.

4.1.4. Space Syntax

As shown below in Figure 22, there is a possibility of traversing the exhibition in multiple routes, but the limited number of rooms narrows down the possibilities. Room A

could be traversed from either the left or the right side, it can be explored slowly as there are multiple objects that are not visible at first sight and can only be seen at certain positions and some even at certain heights in the circuit made by artworks 1, 2, and 3, it is possible to circle the room and to traverse clockwise or counter clockwise, either way, both sides of the room join at the back leading to room B with two openings at its sides leading to the remaining rooms, room C to the right side, and room D on the left. Rooms B, C, and D can be traversed freely.

Figure 22. Possible Routes of Visitor Traversal

The arrangement of objects is complex but manageable, even without the help of contextual objects, and even before watching ‘Compound’ the exhibition displays a minimal narration, an allegory can be inferred, as a very brief anecdote situated in the context of a ritual. The different elements show a representation inside a representation. There is linearity and causality, discomfort and uniqueness.

The hierarchy between TMIs stays in place while considering all artistic and non-artistic objects. Even while there are multiple groups and circuits of objects ‘Compound Eyes of Tropical’ is the main artwork. Only after watching it completely can the whole significance of the artistic objects emerge. The diorama in room A has to be seen

again on the way back, and it now holds more meaning, the characters and actions that happened simultaneously in the short film are now differentiated.

The topography of 'Compound' is informed by the diorama and artworks 5, and 6. Technical aspects of the production become evident when artworks I, and II are seen closely. Visitors can wonder if the animation was shot on the diorama or if the puppets were figured in the short film.

While obscured all rooms are lit in a way that the presence of other visitors is felt, and there is enough space to traverse even if the exhibition space is crowded. There is no presence of the artist or staff. Audience participation is reduced to viewer mode, interactivity functions as virtual agency only, especially in two instances, looking for multiple objects on the diorama and resignifying after watching 'Compound Eyes of Tropical'. This kind of intellectual interaction between spectator and object is aided by the position and size of the objects in the diorama.

The size and position of the objects are also relevant for 'Paper Skin', the visitor is suddenly surrounded by a giant version of the same textures seen in the diorama, but it is now on a larger scale. The small and still puppets used in the diorama also change scale while projected on the TMIs. The visitor becomes part of the exhibition's universe, and yet there are enough traces of material evidence to never become fully immersed, such as references to the craft of animation, both in the movement and in the use of paper, references to the event using a countdown before the next loop, presence of the screen and the projector in the 'Untitled' room, and the intended presence of other visitors.

The use of paper is culturally relevant, as it is used in Taiwan and other parts of East Asia in religious rituals and funerals. Burning models of clothes, houses, and even money as an offering is a tradition in many parts of the country. Zhang Xu-zhan was born into a family that owns a paper sculpture store and has been involved with this tradition for generations. Knowing these facts the main material in the exhibition also gets resignified.

4.1.5. Qualitative interpretation

The elements of 'Jungle, Jungle', the relationship between artworks, and how they are arranged around rooms allows a constant reinterpretation of what was seen before. Most works are related and inform each other. There is a major shift in the reinterpretation of the artworks after watching the central piece 'Compound Eyes of Tropical'. It could be even considered that the whole exhibition functions as an expanded experience for a built

around a short film, other elements can be read as accessories to the film, expanding the anecdote, clearing the intentions, making the size and materials of the figures evident.

The exhibition follows the norms required by a large Contemporary Art venue, inscribed in the parameters of a temporary exhibition, that has adapted the artworks and structured itself around the available space. It goes beyond the norms of exhibition of an animated film. One prominent example of working under such norms is the availability of optative information about the artist, the artworks, and their cultural relevance, in the form of audio guides and booklets. If interested any visitor could have access to this information, or opt not to have any information before entering the exhibition space.

There is a clear divide between the shared TFAM space and that assigned to 'Jungle, Jungle'. The visitor has to decide to enter a narrow hallway and has only a few hints of what is inside, shards of glass and their reflection, the title of the exhibition -and its graphical identity-, a stand with booklets. There is no assigned time to enter, other than the working hours of the Museum.

Once inside, the piece belongs to itself, TFAM was left behind, it seems that it is up to the visitor how much time to spend inside and where to go, there is free traversal and time management. The central part of the experience is well hidden. The diorama has a complex level of detail and a large amount of elements within it. At this point the visitor could construct an overall impression of the exhibition, beyond this central room, the next one is partially visible, on the walls individual paper figures are displayed. The traversal options of the visitors and the presentation of the piece invite them to make a decision that answers the question: is it worth it to spend my time here? The topography of the diorama, the level of detail, and the character-like nature of some of the figures suggest the importance of the groups of characters and their actions, as the ones that are easier to see seem to be more important than those that are hidden. The relationship between hidden and visible figures is not apparent at first sight, as it isn't apparent that some of the characters are human figures with animal costumes on top.

The TMIs are mostly at the very back of the exhibition, they are different from each other, in size, position, intent, projection and screen technology. Materiality is of the utmost importance inside and outside the profilmic space, as evidence of the apparatus, evidence of the artificiality of the moving image.

There is a well defined relationship between the material used -paper-, its cultural significance in the Taiwanese context, and the authors biography. As an outsider to Taiwan this point might not be evident. The association of funerary rites and paper is a very

particular one, and it truly adds a layer of meaning to the piece as a whole. There is a level of fragility intrinsic to paper. Another level of its use as a communication device. The surface becomes significant and informs the style of the piece.

‘Jungle, Jungle’ comes from the cultural periphery using an Asian vernacular tradition for its material form, vernacular Asian sources for its story, character's, representations of traditional musical instruments and clothing. On the other hand it applies techniques from the cultural center to display and exhibit its content.

4.2. ‘Compound Eyes of Tropical’ by Zhang Xu-Zhan

This second case study particularly aims to apply the Methodology of Formal Analysis for Art Installations based on Technical Moving Images to a standardized single-channel exhibition of a short film in a movie theater.

The subject in question is the short animated film that functioned as the main artistic object in the Art Installation ‘Jungle, Jungle’ without any of the surrounding elements or artistic objects.

For all intents and purposes, the profilmic attributes discussed in the previous case study stand for this one.

4.2.1. General Characteristics

‘Compound Eyes of Tropical’ was temporarily shown on the seventh and twenty-eight of April 2023, at Taiwan Film and Audiovisual Institute (TFAI), as part of a program called ‘Compound Eyes of Tropical + selected works by Zhang Xu Zhan’. Its non-commercial public exhibition followed the Institute’s guidelines. TFAI was founded in 1978 and it aims to preserve, restore, research, and promote film and audiovisual cross-media collections and studies.

The site- generic DCP projection without dialogue or subtitles consisted of the following short films:

- Compound Eyes of Tropical. Color, 17 min. 2022.
- Si So Mi. Color, 5min. 2017-2018.
- Ritual of Cathode Ray Tube. B&W, 5min. 2011-2013
- Animation daily series no.1-no.19. B&W, 5min. 2012-2015

The style of the short film is unified, with a handcrafted appearance, seemingly rough surfaces made of paper, bits of thin layered plastic, or shattered mirrors. It shows a figurative representation of a ritual, staring slim and angular anthropomorphic puppets of either animals or humanoid figures wearing costumes of anthropomorphic animals, there

are also accessories for the puppets such as musical instruments, and there are other elements conforming to the environment where the puppets are placed, such as rivers, mountains, and trees, all of these elements are slightly asymmetric, use subdued tones of color, with a predominating earthy and green color palette. The overall tone is somber. Characteristics of the Technical Moving Images.

Contextual documentation was available digitally and printed on publications available at the venue. The context of the exhibition was the following:

‘Born into a family of joss paper artisans in Xinzhuang, the winner of Golden Horse Awards Best Animated Short Zhang Xu Zhan established Hsin Hsin Joss Paper Store to promote Taiwan’s paper offering craft and culture education. Zhang Xu specializes in expressing art with animation, playing with cinema, experimental shorts, video installations, multi-channel projections and sculptures. With an eccentric style, Zhang Xu incorporates contemporary life experiences to discuss the complications of existence, focusing on personal observations of how paper offering legacies and craft stand in society and culture.

At TFAI this month, the compound universe of Zhang Xu’s complete shorts will be presented on the silver screen, and all screenings will be followed by a session with the director.’(TFAI, 2023)

A summary of the short film read:

‘The film is inspired by the costumes of "folk parade" performers from Taiwan's ceremonial festivals. Originally adapted from the Southeast Asian folktale The Mouse Deer Crosses the River, the work integrates similar folklore narratives from different countries to create the half-mouse deer, half-fox shaman puppet dancer in the animation. The dancer switches back and forth between human and animal, using his wit to fool the crocodiles in the river, in an attempt to reach the other side.’(TFAI, 2023)

The contextual information once again validates the cultural significance of the project, streamlines the narrative, and narrows ambiguity. This exhibition downplays the

Southeast Asian connections and instead focuses on the film awards the author has received. It once again mentions the cultural significance of the artist's background and the relationship with the materials used.

It is also noted that every projection will have the presence of the director.

4.2.2. Characteristics of the Technical Moving Image

‘Compound Eyes of Tropical’ was projected in a completely conditioned movie theater on a horizontal screen, the projector is not audible or visible. All content in the profilmic space was acquired optically and featured a figurative representation using paper models in stop-motion animation. The movement is perceptible and almost continuous, small imperfections are present as part of a handmade technical process common to stop-motion animation. The film is self-contained and doesn’t rely on other objects.

4.2.3. Spatial Montage

There is only one mode of TMI in one circuit. All content was intended to be seen during the event and played once on a single channel without a relationship with other channels.

4.2.4. Space Syntax

There were other artistic objects present during the exhibition on the same screen but were meant to be self-contained. All Non-Artistic Objects were meant to be disregarded. There was only one path available during the exhibition and it was confined to a seated position in front of the large screen, there were slight variations from every seated position meant to be disregarded. The complexity of the arrangement was meant to be as simple as possible.

During the projection audience participation was reduced to viewer mode, interactivity was reduced to a virtual agency only, the presence of other spectators and the bodily involvement of the audience, the relation between spectators, and that of spectators and objects were also meant to be disregarded. However, after the projection some of those relationships changed as the Director and Producer addressed the audience by giving some contextual information, and then proceeded to a session of Q&A, so the presence of others, the bodily involvement of the audience, and the relation between spectators were now relevant and the audience could interact directly with the artist in an intellectual discussion, with virtual agency over the artistic objects, going into player mode if wanted.

The materials used also became culturally significant, for the same reasons as in the previous case study, as paper plays an important role both in the movie and in the artist's life.

4.2.5. Qualitative interpretation

There is an impossibility of traversal and time management during the exhibition as it has an assigned event time and the visitors get an assigned seat in the movie theater.

The relationship between the screen size is determined by factors outside of the artist control. The relation between the artwork and the audience shows a power imbalance that is continued even by the presence of the author after the projection, as it starts with an exposition of the background and intent of the work. After that there is a possibility of direct interaction in the session of questions and answers session. The interaction help the reinterpretation of the works after hearing the author's point of view.

Materiality in this case study becomes virtual, as it exist only inside the screen. Evidence of the apparatus is minimized outside of the profilmic space, it only remains inside the frame with evidence of the artificiality of the moving image. Thus cultural relevance of the material is less evident, there are less possibilities to know about -or experience- the cultural significance of paper.

The animated film has vernacular Asian sources for its story, character's, representations of traditional musical instruments and clothing. They are presented within centralized norms of exhibition.

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5. Conclusion

A surface can temporarily be inscribed with a meaningful abstraction processed by a technological source; that inscription can transform over time giving the impression of movement within the surface. In order to inscribe the meaning individuals need to watch it. Significant relationships between the surfaces temporarily inscribed with meaning and the individuals are informed by the way in which the phenomenon is presented in time and space, and by the materials used in its construction. To analyze phenomena regarding moving images in its entirety there is a need to go beyond the virtual space constructed inside the confinement of the surface and regard the complex set of variables in the surrounding spaces and the individuals experiencing the phenomena.

Art Installations based on Technical Moving Images hold the potential to delinearize the discourse associated with single-channel video, by conforming circuits of moving images that are at the same time discrete and related to other discrete sources of moving images.

5.1. Research findings

A) A specific set of qualitative and quantitative tools have been used as a methodology of formal analysis and been applied to the unstandardized art practice of Art Installations, by correlating specific variables elements and determining their purpose it is possible to define the relevance of those variables in the overall piece.

In summary the methodology requires the **definition of the general characteristics of the art installation** (including a description of all the artistic and non-artistic objects, defining its style, defining its site and time specificity, and the intended purpose of the piece), the **definition of the characteristics of the technical moving images used in the art installation** (describing its modes of practice, types of movement, use of channels, replayability, figurativeness and image process origin), the **analysis of the relationship between all technical moving images** (it analyzes the relationship between modes of practice, circuits of moving images, intent in content length and scope, the level of self-containment and reliance on other objects, and the spatial and temporal relationships between them), and the **analysis of the relationship between all objects and individuals in the art installation** (including the possible paths to experience the art installation, the relationship between groups of objects, the intent in the complexity of arrangement, the bodily involvement of the audience, the presence of the artist or staff,

the intended corporeal effects, the relationship between objects and visitors, the intended material evidence or confinement of the exhibition, and the relevance of the materials used). By applying this analysis it is possible to study the internal coherence of the piece or to determine the lack of coherence.

B) This research groups a large number of artistic practices under one theoretical common ground. Among others, animation, film, light art, screen art, projection art, video games, and virtual reality are referred to as Technical Moving Images because they all function as a surface temporarily inscribed with a meaningful abstraction processed by a technological source that holds the potential to transform over time.

Under this principle, other variables such as levels of figurativeness, narrativity, or interactivity associated with each practice, which could previously make them seem highly dissimilar, become mere factors to be considered within a group of related disciplines.

C) The resulting methodology from this thesis can be applied to other modes of artistic practice that use Technical Moving Images.

Analyzing the relevance or irrelevance of the variables will inform how that particular mode of practice relates to a larger group of possibilities that might have become overlooked such as the corporeality of the audience and the materiality of the exhibition in film.

Staying with film as an example, once those possibilities of multi-channel syntagmes are revealed, and other elements of space montage and syntax are taken into consideration by a researcher, it is quite difficult to go back to previous authors that analyze only the pro-filmic space of single-channel films, even when analyzing themes as materiality or the limits in the construction of filmic time and space.

5.2. Further research

I) The research done in this thesis can be adapted for artists that wish to put into practice Art Installations based on Technical Moving Images.

As discussed in Chapter 1 a previous version of this methodology was derived from an academic tool for undergraduate film production students. A revised version meant as a production aid could be developed.

One major similarity between this research meant to be applied for finalized pieces at an exhibition stage, and one meant as a development or pre-production tool is the simple yet effective systematic questioning about the relevance of every element and relationship between elements in the construction of an art installation.

II) The methodology of this research could also be helpful as a qualitative tool to understand the cultural significance in the construction of time, the construction of space, the acknowledgment of the corporeality of the user, and the materiality of the elements in vernacular art forms that use technical moving images along with other objects.

Applying the methodology to just one case study is not enough. The case of 'Jungle, Jungle' might have been beneficial or detrimental to the research, as some of the variables might have fitted the purpose of the study specifically, as might be the case for the relationship between the study of material significance and the use of paper in the piece. That said, another case study might have presented the same kind of functional equivalents in other areas. The studied case might have also been too close to figurative cinema and a more abstract and interactive example could have been beneficial.

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Biography of the author

Secretary General of the National School of Filmic Arts of the National Autonomous University of Mexico. With more than 20 years of experience in the film industry, as both Non-fiction Film Director and Director of Photography with clients including the American Academy of Motion Picture Arts and Sciences, Discovery Networks Latin America, Sony Channel Latin America, and Netflix.

Graduated from the National School of Filmic Arts of the National Autonomous University of Mexico, where he specialized in Documentary Film and Cinematography. He has been a professor at this institution for over a decade. Founding member of the Academic Committee in the University Program of Asian and African Studies. National Journalism Award in the category of Science and Culture 2017.

